

Nature-based reef solution for coastal protection and marine biodiversity enhancement

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Baseline report

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1 Introduction

The primary aim of the project work package “Habitat and biodiversity baseline, monitoring, evaluation and KPI” (WP2) is to provide the necessary habitat and biodiversity baseline (*ante operam*, the condition prior to the activity taking place) of the marine and coastal areas at the **Bevano river mouth** (Fig. 1) to allow the proper design and implementation of the “basal limestone reef” (WP3) and the superimposed biogenic reefs (WP4). This baseline provides the reference condition for the subsequent habitat and biodiversity monitoring, necessary to evaluate the achievement of the project objectives in terms of habitat and species conservation, and biodiversity and reef restoration (see the Key Performance Indicators - KPI; Ponti 2024).

In the first year of the project, a complete characterization of habitats, environmental conditions, communities, and their biodiversity has been carried out within the intervention and monitoring areas of the **Bevano river mouth** (Fig. 1 and Fig. 2). The obtained data and maps define a baseline for the subsequent monitoring and assessment of the achievement of the set objectives. The data needed for properly designing the “basal limestone reef” (WP3) and the biogenic reefs, by seeding native oysters and sabellariid worms (WP4), has been acquired in strict collaboration with the engineers, geologists, and biologists in charge, and transferred to the respective teams as soon as available. All the baseline survey data has been integrated, mapped, analysed, and collected in this baseline report. The baseline includes the following four components, coordinated by PROAMBIENTE and mutually interconnected:

- **Terrain and marine morphology**
- **Metocean conditions**
- **Evolution of coastline, beach-dune system morphology, and vegetation cover**
- **Soft bottom habitats, communities, and biodiversity**
- **Ornithofauna**

Fig. 1. General project area map (basemap Google Maps; Projection UTM33 WGS84, depth MSL).

2 Site description

The area of the estuary of the Bevano river, located in the municipality of Ravenna (Emilia-Romagna Region, Italy), includes one of the rare stretches of coast of the region that are still not urbanized and lacking in intense tourist development (Fig. 2). It is the only river mouth in the region free to evolve following the natural dynamics of sedimentary coastal systems, and the area represents a naturalistic oasis characterised by transitional ecotones between fresh, brackish and marine waters and between wooded, dune and beach systems. Its terrestrial and water habitats have an important ecological role as breeding and nursery areas. For these reasons the entire area, that is an Italian state-owned area, was totally dedicated to nature conservation (100%) and designated as NATURA 2000 site (code [IT4070009](#), named “Ortazzo, Ortazzino, Foce del Torrente Bevano”; Fig. 1 and Fig. 3).

The IT4070009 site has a total surface area of 1255 ha, without any kind of urbanisation, and extends seaward from the coastline for about 300 m, on average. It has 64 ha of coastal area including submerged dunes, emerged dunes and areas behind the dunes.

The **project area**, hereafter named **Bevano river mouth**, is represented by a central portion of the marine and coastal area close to the Bevano river estuary and totally inside the IT4070009 Natura 2000 site.

Fig. 2. Northward aerial photograph of the Bevano river estuary, lagoons and coastal areas. In the background are Lido di Dante and Lido Adriano villages, at the Fiumi Uniti estuary, and offshore gas platforms.

Fig. 3. Habitat map adapted from the official cartography provided by the Emilia-Romagna Region; planned monitoring and intervention areas are indicated (Projection UTM33 WGS84, depth MSL).

The designated managing authority of the site IT4070009 is the Management Body for Parks and Biodiversity - Po Delta, which is a beneficiary partner of this project (DELTA_PO). In this area, coastal management is attributed by the Emilia-Romagna Region to the Municipality of Ravenna, which is also a beneficiary partner of this project (RAVENNA). Moreover, the land area, including the historic pine forest, is a State Reserve and is managed and patrolled by the Carabinieri Command for the Protection of Biodiversity and Parks. In the project area, access to the dunes and landing from the sea are perennially forbidden. Access to most of the beach is completely forbidden during the nesting period of the Kentish plover (*Charadrius alexandrinus*, Italian name: fratino), from 1st of March to 15th July (Fig. 4).

The project area includes the estuary of the Bevano river, a system of brackish lagoons, and behind the coastal dunes a historical pine forest (*Pinus pinaster*). Almost all types of northern Adriatic halophilous vegetation are present in this area. The terminal stretch of the river is characterized by a variety of sandy and muddy bottoms that are home to natural Pacific oyster (*Magallana gigas*) beds which house a high marine biodiversity and protect the riverbanks. The bottom is also rich in estuarine shrimps (*Upogebia pusilla*) and Manila clams (*Ruditapes philippinarum*) (Abbiati et al. 2019).

Fig. 4. Impassable limit along the beach, coming from the north, during the nesting period.

The seabed in front of the mouth is sandy and home to rich soft benthic communities and natural populations of clams (*Chamelea gallina*), a species of high commercial importance (Fig. 5). In a recent study carried out in the whole area, including the Bevano river estuary, 105 taxa were found; however, species richness in the sandy bottom varied from 3 to 30 species, according to depth and the river mouth influence (Fig. 6; Novindi 2020).

Fig. 5. Bevano marine coastal area: on the left fine sand distribution; on the right the distribution of the clam *Chamelea gallina* (from Abbiati et al. 2019; basemap Google Maps, Map projection UTM33 WGS84, depth MSL).

The project area is seriously threatened by coastal erosion, saline intrusion and flooding due to the lack of natural nourishment of the beaches, subsidence, sea level rise and increase in frequency and intensity of storm surges (Martinelli et al. 2010, Armaroli & Duo 2018; Fig. 7). Subsidence is a widespread phenomenon in the Emilia-Romagna, particularly important along the coast because the coastal system consists of sandy beaches and coastal wetlands (Taramelli et al. 2015). The coasts are affected by a marked natural subsidence, because of tectonic processes and recent sediment consolidation. Since the second half of the last century, the subsidence of this area has increased significantly due to intense gas extraction and groundwater exploitation (Bonaldo et al. 2019, Calabrese et al. 2021; Fig. 8).

Fig. 6. Species richness in the Bevano marine coastal area (from Novindi 2020; basemap Google Maps, Map projection UTM33 WGS84, depth MSL).

Fig. 7. Flooding events near the Bevano river mouth due to storm surges and intense rain in 2015.

The combined effects of subsidence and sea level rise, predicted according to the different climate change scenarios, make this area at high risk of flooding, with ever shorter return times (Sekovski et al. 2015, Harley et al. 2016, Perini et al. 2016, Perini et al. 2017; Fig. 9).

Fig. 8. On the left, isokinetic contours maps of land subsidence 2011-2016 around the project area (dashed line), on the right, the shoreline position at the nearby Fiumi Uniti River mouth in the period 1917-1998 (from Calabrese et al. 2021).

Fig. 9. Floodable regions around the project area (dashed line) in the case of a storm surge with 100 years return period under different scenarios (L = “best” and H = “worst” sea level rise scenarios; adapted from Perini et al. 2017).

2.1 Importance of the project area for biodiversity conservation

LIFE NatuReef project mainly aims to restore ancient **oyster and sabellariid worm reefs** at demonstrative scale along the coast of the **Bevano river mouth** with the dual purpose to improve marine biodiversity, including the re-establishment of native protected and non-protected species, and to provide a natural coastal defence against erosion processes, saline intrusion and flooding events, which are increasing in frequency and intensity due to climate change.

Today coastal biogenic reefs along the Mediterranean coasts are very rare because of the many local and widespread anthropogenic threats and the effects of climate change (Ponti et al. 2021). In particular, in the northern Adriatic Sea these habitats are represented by a few marginal native sabellariids (*Sabellaria alveolate* and *S. spinulosa*) worm reefs, still present also in the surrounding areas (Ingrosso et al. 2018, Sanfilippo et al. 2020),

including within this NATURA 2000 site (Fig. 10), and by occasional non-native Pacific oyster beds (*Magallana gigas*, previously known as *Crassostrea gigas*), known also inside the estuary of the Bevano river (Abbiati et al. 2019, Ezgeta-Balic et al. 2019). However, in the northern Adriatic Sea, both historical and palaeoecological evidences reveal the ancient presence of extensive native oyster beds that persisted until the early 20th century, when they fallen victim to multiple anthropogenic impacts, mainly bottom trawling, and were replaced by an infauna-dominated community indicative of instability, disturbance and organic enrichment (Gubbay et al. 2016; Mautner et al. 2018).

Fig. 10. Present sabellariid reef at Lido di Dante in the northern part of this NATURA 2000 site, IT4070009 (courtesy of L. Monteleone).

Mediterranean oyster and sabellariid worm reefs, are biogenic concretions listed in the **NATURA 2000** habitat types (code **1170** - Reefs), often associated with littoral sandbanks (code **1110**), both considered as not priority (European Commission - DG Environment 2013). These reefs belong to the Mediterranean infralittoral biogenic habitats (**EUNIS code MB25**) and to the Mediterranean Sea Habitat Group of the **European Red List of Habitats**. In particular, the **Mediterranean infralittoral oyster beds** (Red list code **A5.6w**), made by the European flat oyster *Ostrea edulis*, are considered as **Endangered** (Gubbay et al. 2016). While the **Polychaete worm reefs in the Mediterranean infralittoral zone** (Red list code **A5.61**), built by the sabellariids *Sabellaria alveolata* and *S. spinulosa*, are considered Data Deficient, however many recent scientific papers support the biodiversity importance and the decline of these habitats along the coasts of the Mediterranean Sea (e.g., Gravina et al. 2018 Ingrassio et al. 2018, Bonifazi et al. 2019).

Although the restoration of oyster and sabellariid worm reefs will be realized at sea (see possible intervention area in Fig. 3), building up **biogenic barrier reefs** within 200 m off the coast, its protective effects against erosion processes, saline intrusion and flooding events will extend to the corresponding shore and nearby habitats of the **Bevano river mouth**. Therefore, the project **LIFE NatuReef** other than restore historically lost habitats, will largely contribute to protect and enhance a relevant subset of the priority and non-priority habitat types already included in this Natura 2000 site (see monitoring area in Fig. 3):

1110 - Sandbanks which are slightly covered by sea water all the time

1130 - Estuaries

1150 - Coastal lagoons*

1210 - Annual vegetation of drift lines

1310 - *Salicornia* and other annuals colonizing mud and sand

1320 - *Spartina* swards (*Spartinion maritimae*)

1410 - Mediterranean salt meadows (*Juncetalia maritimi*)

2110 - Embryonic shifting dunes

2120 - Shifting dunes along the shoreline with *Ammophila arenaria* ('white dunes')

2130 - Fixed dunes with herbaceous vegetation* ('grey dunes')

2270 - Wooded dunes with *Pinus pinea* and/or *Pinus pinaster**

6420 - Mediterranean tall humid grasslands of the *Molinio-Holoschoenion*

* = Natura 2000 priority habitat

LIFE NatuReef project, enhancing marine habitats and biodiversity, aims to provide better conditions for endangered species already present in the area, like the loggerhead sea turtle *Caretta caretta* (listed in: Habitat directive Annex 2 and 4; Berna convention Annex 2; CITES Annex A; Bonn convention Annex 1; Specially Protected Areas of Mediterranean Importance - SPAMI Annex 2; Vulnerable in the IUCN Mediterranean Red List of Species). The biogenic reefs will also provide habitat for other protected and/or endangered species documented here in the past or known associated with similar reefs in the Adriatic Sea, like the seahorses *Hippocampus hippocampus* and *H. guttulatus* (both listed in: CITES Annex D; Specially Protected Areas of Mediterranean Importance - SPAMI Annex 2; Data Deficient in the IUCN Mediterranean Red List of Species).

Moreover, **LIFE NatuReef** project, providing coastal defence against erosion processes, saline intrusion and flooding events, will provide protection for many endangered coastal species, like:

- *Charadrius alexandrinus** (Kentish plover; Fig. 11)
- *Sterna albifrons** (= *Sternula albifrons*, little tern; Fig. 12)

* Bird Directive Annex I

Fig. 11. Kentish plover, *Charadrius alexandrinus*, photographed by G. Melandri at Bevano river mouth, Jul 22, 2021 (iNaturalist.com).

Fig. 12. Little tern, *Sterna albifrons*, photographed by Goblekitepe at Po River delta, May 1, 2021 (iNaturalist.com).

3 Terrain and marine morphology

3.1 Bathymetric survey

The geophysical inspection of ultra-shallow environments like the one under study in the Bevano area was until today almost impractical due to very low water depth, chaotic waves, tides, and currents. However, in recent years new technologies have been developed and made ready to the market that changed the situation a lot. Today the availability of small but powerful electronics, some of them released with Open-Hardware/Open-Software licenses, allowed the development of small aquatic surface vehicles able to navigate autonomously given a planned route. The ability to follow the planned paths with very high precision, unthinkable to a human manned boat, unleash the ability to perform real 4D geophysical investigations also in the shallow and ultra-shallow area facing the shoreline. The **OpenSWAP ASV** (Autonomous Surface Vehicle) is a class of autonomous vehicles, of different sizes and weights (Fig. 13) developed with the aim to navigate autonomously following a planned route with a precision higher than ~30 cm (Stanghellini et al. 2020). They were developed from scratch by a Proambiente/CNR-Ismar collaboration and made available to the market in 2020. They were used extensively during the research project TAO, funded by the Emilia Romagna Region with the purpose to develop a system able to monitor and investigate coastal erosion and mitigation. Besides that, being internally developed, it is possible to eventually optimize the system to adapt to the investigated environment (in this case, the Bevano area).

Fig. 13. OpenSWAP Autonomous Surface Vehicle (www.openswap.it).

The goals of these repeated surveys are to obtain the morpho-bathymetric maps of the area to study the initial state (the baseline) and the evolution in the following 3 years, through the comparison and comparative analysis of the collected data. The backscatter images of the seabed also have significant input to the production of thematic maps on the state of the seabed (e.g., habitat mapping) and from the morphological point of view: sediment thickness map - sediment distribution maps - erosion vs. deposition analysis (Del Bianco et al. 2014). All measurements respect high hydrographic standards and are normalized with the aid of a local hydrometric station recording the variation of tide levels continuously.

Within the initial study aimed at "capturing" the current state of the area involved in the LIFE NatuReef project, a bathymetric survey of the seabed was also conducted. Given that this is a transitional zone where water depths are extremely shallow and considering the need to collect data in proximity to the shoreline, the use of a single beam echosounder was preferred. This choice enabled the survey to achieve extremely low depths in "ultra-shallow water" conditions. The measurements were conducted during high tide to access areas closer to the shoreline.

The bathymetric baseline survey was made in 2024-03-14, with the use of ASV (Autonomous Surface Vehicle) OpenSWAP (Stanghellini, Del Bianco, e Gasperini 2020) equipped with a single beam echosounder.

3.1.1 Single beam echosounder

Bathymetric data were collected using a vertical incidence single-beam echosounder developed in a collaboration between ISMAR-CNR and Proambiente Scrl of Bologna. This is characterized by a high operating frequency (50-200 kHz), narrow (8° conical) beam width, short pulse length (350 μs), and a minimum depth range of ~0.3 m (Table 1). The 200 kHz echo-sounder signal was digitally sampled along a constant time window (15 ms) encompassing water column, seafloor, and sub-seafloor, and the echograms were stored in SEG-Y-format files (Fig. 14).

Table 1. Parameters of the Single Beam Echosounder.

Single Beam Echosounder	
Transducer brand	Airmar - 8° beam angle
Emitted frequency	50 - 200 KHz (selectable)
Depth Accuracy	1 cm/0.1% of depth (0.5 to 40m)
Pulse length	350 μsec - (variable)
N. of samples	10000 for each pulse
Data Format Acquisition	SEG-Y and NMEA \$DPT + water temperature

High frequency profiles information is

200 kHz

- High precision depth (bathymetric maps)
- Water column information
- Bottom information (reflectivity \gg grain size)
- Fine sediment depocenters

Fig. 14. Example of an echographic profile acquired using a single-beam echosounder operating at a frequency of 200 kHz. The types of information that can be extracted from the analysis of water column reflectivity are clearly visible.

This instrument is capable of recording the entire echogram of the water column, allowing for the acquisition of various levels of information. The first level of information relates to point-specific depth, i.e., the positioning of the water/sediment interface, which provides the depth of the seabed with centimeter-scale vertical accuracy. The second level of information pertains to the acoustic response throughout the water column and in the uppermost sediment layers, provided they are fine and unconsolidated. By leveraging this "reflectivity index," it is possible to estimate the sediment granulometry and reconstruct the very first layers of any stratification present near the seabed.

This instrumentation was installed aboard OpenSWAP ASV capable of retracing the same route with a maximum error contained in +/- 30 cm in reasonable sea conditions (Stanghellini et al. 2020).

3.1.2 GNSS receiver

The GNSS receiver U-blox RTK ZED-F9P is used in a dual configuration to determine the true heading of the moving vehicle. This setup involves a moving base and a moving rover, both equipped with L1/L2 antennas. The position

correction relies on a Network Real-Time Kinematic (NRTK) service, which uses Virtual Reference Stations (VRS). RTCM correction data is transmitted via the internet to a 4G link, which is connected to a Raspberry Pi. The Raspberry Pi receives the RTCM data in real-time via the 4G link and processes it through a USB connection to the GNSS receivers, enabling accurate position correction and heading determination (Fig. 15).

Fig. 15. Diagram of the dual U-blox RTK ZED-F9P GNSS receiver setup for vehicle heading determination using RTCM corrections.

3.1.3 Data processing

After frequency filtering and offset corrections between the transducers and the GNSS antenna, an algorithm of bottom detection was employed to automatically identify the depth of the seabed (bottom tracking). That transit time, the so-called TWT (two-way travel), was converted into depth (m) using the average speed of sound in seawater (1505 m/s, on average) measured at the beginning and end of each survey.

This data was finally elaborated with GMT (Wessel et al. 2013) with its near-neighbour and grid filter algorithms to obtain the map illustrated in the last section of this document. A GNSS system w/double GPS receiver using RTK correction provided the positioning during the survey.

The dataset is provided in four formats:

- GRID NetCFD – Geographic coordinates DD.XXXXXX - WGS84 (EPSG:4326)
- XYZ AsciiText File containing (Lat, Lon, Depth) - Geographic coordinates DD.XXXXXX - WGS84 (EPSG:4326)
- XYZ AsciiText File containing (Y, X, Depth) – Projected meters UTM33 – WGS84 (EPSG: 32633)

- GEOTiff image format

3.1.4 Survey route planning

The planned route was designed to cover the study area with line spacing adjusted to account for the estimated bathymetric variation, in accordance with previously acquired data from earlier measurement campaigns (Stanghellini et al., 2022). Consideration was given to the presence of a transverse breakwater located immediately north of the investigated area (Fig. 16).

Fig. 16. Navigation route: Acquisition line grid of echographic and seismic reflection; Background: Orthophoto AGEA 2020 (r_emiro:2022-03-10T115056), map coordinate system WGS84/UTM33 (EPSG 32633).

The straight-line paths were executed using fully automated navigation. Conversely, the irregular lines within the intertidal zone were conducted in a mixed manual/semi-automatic mode, enabling investigation of areas closest to the minimum depths detectable by the instrument (approximately 20-30 cm). In several instances, the vehicle became stranded in the sediment, requiring operator intervention to free it from the seabed.

The ground station was strategically located on the beach at a central point along the navigation route to maintain visual contact with the vehicle. This positioning enabled the ground station to effectively manage data acquisition from the echosounder and ensure accurate navigation of the ASV OpenSWAP along the specified route.

3.2 Topographic survey

The baseline survey of the emerged portion of the Bevano river mouth area was made in march, exploiting an integration of techniques: an Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) system embed with both an optical camera and a LiDAR sensor is used for collecting both a visual and metric description of the morphology of the area; GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite System) receivers embed on the UAV system or on a pole are used for georeferencing reason in order to have the final products referred to the right coordinate system: RDN2008/UTM33.

3.2.1 GNSS receiver

The GNSS receiver TopCon Hiper V is used to acquire the position of a network of ground points (Fig. 17). The position correction mode is based on a Network Real Time Kinematic (NRTK) service, exploiting Virtual Reference Stations (VRS).

The GNSS data of these ground points, collected in the geographic system ETRS89-RDN2008 with ellipsoidal height, are converted by the software convER in the projected cartographic system RDN2008/UTM33 with orthometric height, using the IGM (Istituto Geografico Militare) gridded data gk-2, based on the geoid model ITALGEO2005. This data elaboration shows a mean geoid height of 39.039 m, value used for the global shift of the DTMM (Digital Terrain and Marine Model).

The network of ground points is composed by three different types of points: permanent points, based on pins into wood elements; not permanent points, based on circular plywood targets, diameter of 50 cm, with a black and white pattern; not permanent points, based on square plastic targets, 10×10 cm, with a black and white pattern. The location of these ground points is used for the photogrammetric and LiDAR processing: some points are exploited as Ground Control Points and their location is integrated into the elaborations; the remaining points are used as Check points, so their location is used for the evaluation of the reconstruction accuracy.

Fig. 17. Network of the ground points collected on the site by the GNSS receiver TopCon Hiper V in NRTK mode. Background: Orthophoto AGEA 2020 (r_emiro:2022-03-10T115056), map coordinate system RDN2008/UTM33 (EPSG 6708).

3.2.2 UAV system

The UAV flights are made in the area, exploiting the low tide of the day, by the DJI Matrice 300 RTK, 810×670×430 mm (without rotors), max. take-off weight 9 kg, with a max. payload of 2.7 kg, equipped both with the payload P1 (optical camera) and the L1 (LiDAR sensor). The presence of a gimbal onboard the UAV system grants to compensate for the movement of the mount, allowing a stable acquisition during the flight. The position correction mode of the UAV is based on a Network Real Time Kinematic (NRTK) service, exploiting a Virtual Reference Station (VRS) located in proximity of the take-off point.

3.2.2.1 Optical Camera

The UAV photogrammetric survey (Fig. 18, Table 2) is carried out by two planned flights with the DJI Pilot 2 software. The two flights have a total duration of about 36 minutes, capturing 1025 pictures at the fixed height from the take-off point of about 45 m, setting a forward and side overlap respectively of 80% and 60%.

Table 2. Parameters of the UAV photogrammetric flight.

Flight Parameters	
payload name/camera model	DJI Zenmuse P1
payload type	optical camera
sensor dimension	36×24 mm
picture resolution	8192×5460 pixel
focal length	24.00 mm
forward overlap	80%
side overlap	60%
flight height (from take-off point)	45 m
Ground Sampling Distance (GSD)	~ 0.82 cm
flight speed	5.0 m/s
number of flights	2
surveyed area	~ 0.34 km ²
number of images	1025 (477 in the north flight; 548 in the south flight)
flight time	~36 min (18 min for the north flight; 17 min for the south flight)

Fig. 18. Shooting locations during the UAV photogrammetric flights (P1 payload). Background: Orthophoto AGEA 2020 (r_emiro:2022-03-10T115056), map coordinate system RDN2008/UTM33 (EPSG 6708).

The pictures are processed by the photogrammetric software Metashape, based on a Structure-from-Motion approach. In particular, the photogrammetric workflow is composed as follow:

- The shooting location, collected in the geographic system ETRS89-RDN2008 with ellipsoidal height, are converted by the software convER in the projected cartographic system RDN2008/UTM33 maintaining the ellipsoidal height. The images and their new shooting coordinates are imported in Metashape as correct metadata to be processed.
- Tie points detection at the original resolution of the images with a reduction of the computational time thanks to the use of a coarse-to-fine strategy (generic preselection) and the knowledge of the shooting location (reference preselection).
- Computation of the external and internal orientation parameters thanks to the knowledge of the tie points location and the shooting locations.
- Refinement of the bundle-adjustment thanks to the knowledge of the GCPs coordinates and optimization of the camera calibration (f, cx, cy, k1, k2, k3, p1, p2, b1, b2).
- Removal of bad tie points (gradual selection procedure) and alignment optimization.
- Evaluation of the Ground Control Points (d003, d014, cs08, cs04, d004, cs07, q007, d007, cs03, d006) and Checkpoints (q002, d011, d010, q001, d012, d013) errors. The GCPs have a RMSE of about 4.6 cm and a max error of about 8.0 cm (d006); the Checkpoints have a RMSE of about 6.1 cm and a max error of 8.4 cm (q002).
- Dense correlation at high resolution (1/4 of the original images resolution) with a mild filtering.
- Filtering of the dense cloud with the removal of points with a poor quality (are maintained points with a confidence ≥ 3).
- Digital Surface Model generation thanks the interpolation of the filtered dense point cloud (GSD=1.66 cm)
- Orthomosaic generation with a mosaic blending mode, exploiting the DSM as the reference surface. (GSD=0.83 cm)

3.2.2.2 LiDAR

The UAV LiDAR survey (Fig. 19, Table 3) is carried out by two planned flights with the DJI Pilot 2 software. The two flights have a total duration of about 41 minutes, capturing the site by a non-repetitive scanning mode at the fixed height from the take-off point of about 45m, setting a side strip overlap of 20%.

The LiDAR data acquired is processed through the software DJI Terra Pro, setting the input coordinate system (RDN2008)¹ and the output coordinate system (RDN2008/UTM33 with ellipsoidal height; Table 4). It is not made any smoothing process of the cloud roughness, to preserve the scene discontinuity, and the data optimization is made thanks the integration of the observations of a new virtual reference station located on the area (44° 22'2.093"N, 12°19'23.211"E, 50.0 m ellipsoidal height) and of the altitude value of some ground points. The Ground Control

¹ "Rete Dinamica Nazionale 2008" replaced IGM95 as the national geodetic reference system. For the practical habitat mapping purposes of this project, this system can be considered equivalent to WGS84.

Points (d010, d013, d007, d014, d003, d012, d011) have an average RMSE of the altitude difference of about 3.4 cm and the Checkpoints (d004, d006) have an average RMSE of the altitude difference of about 4.4 cm.

The Digital Terrain Model (DTM) generation is made at the resolution of 0.2 m, exploiting the point ground classification with the parameters of the “gentle slope” (iteration angle of 6°, iteration distance of 0.5 m).

Table 3. Parameters of the UAV LiDAR flight.

Flight Parameters	
payload name	DJI Zenmuse L1
payload type	LiDAR sensor with an integrated optical camera
camera model	EP800
sensor dimension (optical camera)	1 inch
focal length (optical camera)	8.8 mm
picture resolution (optical camera)	5472×3648 pixel
side overlap (LiDAR)	20%
forward overlap (optical camera)	70%
side overlap (optical camera)	37%
flight height (from take-off point)	45 m
cloud density	~381 point/m ²
Ground Sampling Distance (optical camera)	~1.23 cm
flight speed	4.7 m/s
return mode	triple
scanning mode	non-repetitive
number of flights	2
surveyed area	~ 0.38 km ²
number of images	746 (375 in the north flight; 371 in the south flight)
estimated time	~41 min (20 min for the north flight; 21 min for the south flight)

Fig. 19. Shooting locations during the UAV LiDAR flights (L1 payload). Background: Orthophoto AGEA 2020 (r_emiro:2022-03-10T115056), map coordinate system RDN2008/UTM33 (EPSG 6708).

3.3 Results

The bathymetric (Fig. 20) and topographic (Fig. 21) data collect two parts of the same reality. The generation of a unique Digital Terrain and Marine Model (DTMM, Fig. 22, Tab.4) is made by using a TIN (Triangulated Irregular Network) interpolation of the LiDAR data (only the ground points) and the bathymetric data. A vertical shift is applied to the combined digital elevation model, corresponding to the mean geoid height (39.039 m), to obtain a description of the area with orthometric values. The photogrammetric workflow is exploited for the generation of an orthomosaic (Tab.4), a visual and metric representation of the area, and of a Digital Surface Model, used as a check element for the evaluation of the coherency of the survey and processing conducted.

Table 4. Parameters of the final outputs: Digital Terrain and Marine Model (DTMM) and Orthomosaic.

Digital Terrain and Marine Model	
Data used	LiDAR points + single beam echosounder points
Interpolation type	TIN
Output resolution	20 cm
Datum	RDN2008/UTM33 with orthometric height
Orthomosaic	
Data used	photos of P1 camera - photogrammetric processing
Output resolution	20 cm
Datum	RDN2008/UTM33

Fig. 20. Bathymetric map; Background: Orthophoto AGEA 2020 (r_emiro:2022-03-10T115056), map coordinate system WGS84/UTM33 (EPSG 32633), depth MSL.

Fig. 21. Orthomosaic of the topographic part (on the left); Digital Terrain Model (DTM) of the topographic part (on the right). Background: Orthophoto AGEA 2020 (r_emiro:2022-03-10T115056), map coordinate system RDN2008/UTM33 (EPSG 6708).

Fig. 22. Digital Terrain and Marine Model (DTMM) of the area. Background: Orthophoto AGEA 2020 (r_emiro:2022-03-10T115056), map coordinate system RDN2008/UTM33 (EPSG 6708).

4 Metocean conditions

In this section we describe the typical wind, waves and current conditions at the study site. The present study is based on hindcast data for wind, waves, currents and physical parameters like temperature and salinity, due to lack in metocean measurements in the area.

Public wind and wave/physics databases have become established as an important and widely utilized resource for the study of atmospheric and oceanic processes. For this study, the following databases have been used:

- CMEMS MED - Waves Reanalysis Hindcasts data,
- ECMWF ERA-5 Wind Reanalysis Hindcasts data,
- CMEMS Phys Reanalysis Hindcasts data.

Metocean data have been taken by the Copernicus Marine Service database², that is the marine service component of the Copernicus program, delivering freely accessible oceanic operational data and information services. It is run by Mercator Ocean and its contractors on behalf of the European Union. Mercator Ocean, Global Ocean Forecasting Centre, is based in Toulouse, France. Details of the validation of the data and their quality are reported in:

<https://resources.marine.copernicus.eu/documents/QUID/CMEMS-MED-QUID-006-004.pdf>

4.1 Wave climate and extreme wave conditions

Data sources used to describe the wave climate are the direct measurements of the Nausicaa wave buoy, managed by the ARPA ER, are provided at:

<https://www.arpae.it/it/temi-ambientali/mare/dati-e-indicatori/dati-boa-ondametrica>.

² <http://marine.copernicus.eu/>

Nausicaa wave data are available since the buoy installation in May 2007. The time-series of HS measured by the Nausicaa wave buoy (blue) and hindcasted at the closest CMEMS grid point (red) is presented in Fig. 23.

Fig. 23. Timeseries of the Significant Wave height From the Nausicaa Buoy (observation) and from the Copernicus data (simulation).

A detail of the comparison is presented in the next figure XX. As we can observe there is a very good match between the 2 data sources and the main difference is the underestimation of the peaks of CMEMS data. For this reason, we have used data from Nausicaa (Observation in Fig. 23 and 24)

Fig. 24. Zoom of comparison between CMEMS and Observation from Nausicaa Buoy

The wave rose of the Nausicaa data is presented in Fig. 25.

Fig. 25. Wave rose plots Nausicaa data 2007-2020.

The extreme wave analysis based on the Nausicaa wave (2007-20222) data was done following the standard POT peak data selection and the Gumbel distribution adaptation. The results are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Extreme wave condition offshore the study site.

T_R (years)	$0^\circ \leq D < 360^\circ$	
	H_s m	T_p s
1	3.37	8.21
2	3.76	8.39
5	4.28	8.61
10	4.66	8.76
25	5.18	8.95
50	5.56	9.08
70	5.75	9.14
100	5.95	9.21
150	6.18	9.28
200	6.34	9.33
500	6.85	9.47
1000	7.24	9.58
<i>Coeff corr</i>	<i>0.9779</i>	

4.1.1 Wave Modelling at the study site

The following simulations were performed to describe the actual state of the wave field and hydrodynamics:

- Wave propagation through a spectral model (MIKE21 SW).
- Hydrodynamic and morphodynamic studies through MIKE 21 HD and ST.
- Shoreline modelling through MIKE21 SM.

To create the calculation mesh of the model, different sources of bathymetric data were used:

- Survey specially carried out in November 2023 as part of the NatuREEF project;
- CMAP digitized nautical chart for depths greater than -10 m.

The result is shown in the following figures. Fig. 26 shows the bathymetry, the DTM at the study area.

Fig. 26. Bathymetry of the study site (UTM33/WGS84, depth MSL).

The mesh is presented in Fig. 27, its dimension is reduced in proximity to the location where the reef will be built. It is evident also the presence of the existing low crested structure northward the study site.

Fig. 27. Mesh used for the Mike21 SW simulation (UTM33/WGS84, depth MSL).

The wave modelling of the actual situation is presented in Fig. 28. The impact of the reef on the wave field and hydrodynamics will be assessed by comparing the actual configuration (absence of the breakwater) with the field view in the presence of the reef.

We have investigated two wave conditions representing the peaks of two different storms typical of the wave climate. Specifically, we have tested sea states characterized by $H_{m0} = 1.4$ m, $T_p = 5.5$ s, MWD = 90 °N (Scirocco, Fig. 28 left) and $H_{m0} = 3.8$ m, $T_p = 7$ s, MWD = 60 °N (Bora, Fig. 28 right), respectively, whose data were recorded by the wave buoy Nausicaa, located on a depth of -10 m, 30 NM south of the study site.

Fig. 28. Storms recorded by the wave buoy Nausicaa and simulated.

The wave field during the storm peaks are represented in the following Fig. 29. Here it is evident the ability of the existing low crested structures breakwater in reducing the wave height and protecting the shore, but also with local effect due to the wave diffraction at the existing breakwater Southern roundhead.

Fig. 29. Map of the significant wave height during a Scirocco storm (top panel) and during a Bora Storm (bottom panel). The simulations refer to the offshore wave conditions in Figure c ($H_{m0} = 1.4$ m, $T_p = 5.5$ s, $MWD = 90^\circ N$ and $H_{m0} = 3.8$ m, $T_p = 7$ s, $MWD = 60^\circ N$) (UTM33/WGS84, depth MSL).

5 Evolution of coastline, beach–dune system morphology, and vegetation cover

5.1 Reference framework

5.1.1 Site description

The intervention area concerns the coastline south of Lido di Dante, within the municipality of Ravenna, located approximately 13 km southeast of the city. This is a sandy coastal stretch situated between the mouth of the Fiumi Uniti to the north and the Bevano stream to the south. The Lido di Dante coastline is part of a highly valuable natural and scenic landscape, as it still preserves remnants of significant morphological features (such as sandy dunes and wet depressions) and plant associations that form rare habitats along the northern Adriatic coast, thus holding considerable conservation interest. Behind the beach lies a section of the extensive pine forest that characterizes the Ravenna coastline (the Ramazzotti pine forest), which was severely affected by a deliberate fire in July 2012, destroying approximately 65 hectares, equivalent to half of the entire forest. As with all sandy coastlines, the area exhibits a highly dynamic evolutionary process, particularly influenced by the presence of the two river mouths that border it.

From a geological perspective, the area is distinguished by a recent evolutionary history, which brought to the natural retreat of emerged land (Armaroli et al. 2013, Balouin et al. 2006, Gardelli 2007, Montanari & Marasmi 2013, Taramelli et al. 2015, Soboyejo et al. 2021). This is primarily due to a reduction in riverine sediment transport, driven by climatic cycles, and the dominance of marine processes over fluvial ones, which has led to the regional straightening of the shoreline.

In addition to this natural trend, human activities in various forms have intensified and accelerated the progression toward a constant and progressive landward retreat. The process of urbanization of Lido di Dante started in the latter half of the 20th century. The initial phase of urbanization, which started in the late 1950s, had a markedly detrimental impact on the area. This was due to the flattening of the coastal dune, which removed the physical natural defence system against marine ingression. Subsequently, the urban core has undergone several phases of growth, with a notable expansion occurring in recent times, beginning in the 2000s. In its present state, the area, which is primarily a summer tourist destination, comprises approximately 200 residential units, the majority of which are second homes. The tourism infrastructure is largely seasonal and is supported mainly by two campsites, one of which is near the beach and the intervention area.

The Bevano River (Fig. 30) originates in the Apennine Mountains and flows into the Adriatic Sea and is the last meandering estuary of the upper Adriatic that is free to evolve naturally. The last section of the Bevano river tends

to migrate northward, and over the past 50 years, it has undergone significant alterations (Fig. 2), mainly due to dominant marine processes, such as longshore currents, and low-energy fluvial regime. This migration has caused rapid erosion of the pine forest, and the coastal dunes located immediately to the north of the river mouth, further complicating the drainage of floodwaters into the sea. For these reasons, in 2006, a functional rehabilitation project for the river mouth was carried out by the Technical Service of the Romagna River Basin Authority of the Emilia-Romagna Region. This project involved the opening of a new river mouth in an intermediate position between the existing one and the last meander, to ensure a continuous water exchange between the sea and the river, even during low tide. Additionally, a channel was opened at the last meander, with a bottom elevation at mean sea level (+ 0.00), allowing water to flow only during high tide or river flood events. The existing mouth was closed using sand material excavated from the new mouths, and part of the eroded dune was reconstructed to protect the pine forest (Fig. 31).

Fig. 30. Bevano river mouth.

Fig. 31. Comparison of aerial photos RAF 1943-44, GAI 1954, RER 1976-78, COSTA RER 1991, 2005 and 2008 (RER, 2009).

This river and its estuary hold substantial environmental and ecological significance, forming an integral part of the Po Delta Regional Park. As a protected natural reserve, the Bevano River and its estuary are renowned for their rich biodiversity, serving as a crucial habitat for a variety of birds, plants, and aquatic life. The estuary and its surrounding wetlands support a diverse array of flora and fauna, making it a vital site for birdwatching. Numerous species of migratory birds use this area as a stopover or breeding ground. Given its ecological importance, significant conservation efforts are in place to protect the habitats within the Bevano River estuary. The estuary of the Bevano river falls within the IT4070009 – SAC / SPA – “Ortazzo, Ortazzino, Foce del Torrente Bevano”. This area is one of the most environmentally diverse coastal sites in the region. It includes the mouth of the Bevano river, 5 km of active coastal dunes backed by a *Pinus pinaster* coastal pine forest, and the Ortazzino and Ortazzo system of brackish peri-fluvial wetlands. The site also extends about 300 m into the coastal marine belt. The mouth of the

Bevano River itself spans approximately 40 hectares and exemplifies the natural balance of water and sand, which changes with seasonal tidal and river flow patterns.

The Emilia-Romagna Regional Agency for Prevention, Environment, and Energy (ARPAE) has strategically divided the regional coastline into seven distinct stretches, known as sedimentary macrocells, which function independently of one another (Fig. 32). This subdivision (SICELL system) allows for more precise and effective management of the coastline, as each macrocell can be monitored and maintained according to its unique environmental conditions and challenges. By treating these segments as separate entities, ARPAE can implement tailored conservation, management and protection measures.

Each macrocell is further subdivided into smaller units known as cells. The NatuReef project area falls within the macrocell M4, and specifically from the northern portion of cell no. 70 to cell no. 71. Between 2000 and 2006, the cell was considered "stable", meaning it was a stretch of coastline that did not show significant sand loss or accumulation and was not subject to coastal defence interventions (such as nourishment or defence structures) during that period". In the following period, from 2006 to 2012, the cell was classified as "eroding," a state defined as a stretch of coastline showing significant sand loss during the examined period (according to the ASPE indicator, accumulations or losses greater than 30 m³/m are considered significant) (Montanari & Marasmi 2014). In the last 10 years, storm surges have worsened the erosion. During the severe storm on January 31, 2014, the stretch of coastline between Lido di Dante and the mouth of the Bevano stream (cell 71, Fig. 32) experienced the complete dismantling of the earth embankment that was built to protect the Ramazzotti pine forest and the hinterland, over a length of approximately 90 m.

Between 2012 and 2018, this area exhibited a stable condition near the river mouth, indicated by the ASPE and ASE indicators in Table 6, while the northern area closest to the urbanized area and the beach establishments of Lido di Dante (cell 71) is characterized by precarious erosion and stability conditions.

Fig. 32. Division of sedimentary macrocell 4 into cells. The barrier area would fall between cells 70 and 71 (ARPAE, 2020³).

³ https://ambiente.regione.emilia-romagna.it/it/suolo-bacino/argomenti/progetti-interventi/difesa-della-costa/allegati/allegati/Tav6_R

Table 6. Changes in the coastline between Marina di Ravenna and the mouth of the Savio river between 2012 and 2018.

Savio mouth - Marina di Ravenna (M4): Volume change (DV), subsidence losses (Vsub), beach nourishments (Vrip), withdrawals (Vpre) and beach condition indicators ASE and ASPE in the period 2012-2018 (lengths in m, volumes in m³).

Cell	Cell name	Length	DV	Vsub	Vrip	Vpre	ASE	ASPE
65	Lido di Classe	1.220	-30.353	7.282	0	0	S	S
66	Lido di Classe Nord	580	-11.114	5.303	0	0	S	S
67	Bevano Sud	1.000	7.289	10.375	0	0	S	S
68	Bevano Centro Sud	1.900	22.083	27.092	0	0	S	S
69	Foce Bevano	110	890	2.949	0	0	-	-
70	Bevano Centro Nord	1.300	8.991	36.414	0	0	S	S
71	Bevano Nord	1.000	-82.377	28.472	87.380	0	E	E
72	Lido di Dante	605	38.147	14.788	38.105	0	A	P
73	Sud Foce Fiumi Uniti	600	39.799	23.208	0	0	A	A
74	Foce Fiumi Uniti	270	-4.527	10.502	0	0	-	-
75	Nord Foce Fiumi Uniti	360	-15.503	10.557	0	0	E	E
76	Lido Adriano	2.560	54.367	51.053	7.390	0	S	P
77	Punta Marina	3.730	130.177	41.652	298.730	0	A	E
78	Punta Marina Nord	865	19.220	9.555	51.400	0	S	E
79	Marina di Ravenna	3.000	43.948	41.297	0	92.100	S	A
	Totale	19.100	221.037	320.499	483.005	92.100		

N.B. In macrocell 4, there are no beach nourishments carried out with sand recovered from the sifting of material from the cleaning of the beaches in this macrocell.

5.1.2 Coastal defences and their effects on the coastline

Beach erosion in Italy is primarily driven by the decrease in sediment supply from rivers and the construction of harbours and other rigid coastal structures, which disrupt the natural dynamics of the beaches (Motta Zanin et al. 2023). To protect Italy's coastlines from erosion and flooding, about 16% of these areas are fortified with "hard" coastal protection measures. This strategy is predominantly used in regions where urban centres, transportation networks, and socio-economic activities are concentrated along the coast (Triglia et al. 2015).

In the context of the Emilia-Romagna region, the Ravenna coastline is particularly vulnerable to coastal erosion primarily because of the limited sediment supply from rivers, land loss due to subsidence (combination of both natural and anthropogenic), as well as increasing frequency of high-energy meteorological and marine events, such as storm surges.

In Ravenna, the coastal zone is characterized by the presence of an array of cross-structures, which are designed to safeguard and preserve the openings of river mouths, canals, and port channels. The shoreline situated to the south of the Fiumi Uniti river mouth (Lido di Dante) is particularly susceptible to substantial erosion. This has resulted in

the gradual retreat of the shoreline over time, necessitating the construction of robust coastal defence structures to safeguard the beach and the surrounding area. Here, hard coastal protection measures include: revetments around Fiumi Uniti river mouth (vertical or sloped structures built parallel to the coast to absorb and reflect wave energy, reducing the impact of storm surges and high tides); groynes (long, narrow structures built perpendicular to the coastline, built to trap sand moving along the coast due to longshore drift, thereby reducing erosion and building up beaches); emerged and submerged breakwaters (offshore structures that protect the shore by breaking the force of incoming waves), and embankment (structures typically made of earth, rocks, or other materials, constructed along coastlines). An example of soft coastal protection measures applied in the project area is the artificial beach nourishment, that involves the use of large quantities of sediment to replace lost sediments and to widen the beach, providing more protection against erosion. Beach nourishment projects are carried out by using sand extracted from offshore sand reservoirs situated on the continental shelf of the Emilia-Romagna region. From 2002 to the present, 3 major beach nourishment works have been carried out in the project coastal area (Lido di Dante): Progettone 2 (2007), Progettone 3 (2016) and Progettone 4 (2022)⁴. These works are in addition to smaller operations carried out by local authorities. Fig. 33a and Fig. 33b show the pre- and post- Progettone 3 conditions in the Bevano estuary area, respectively. Beach nourishment represents a crucial measure to counteract coastal erosion. However, its efficacy is inherently limited by the transitory nature of its impact. The combined influence of natural currents, anthropogenic activities, and climate change continues to exert a constant pressure on the coastline, necessitating the continuous implementation of beach nourishment. This underscores the imperative to identify alternative strategies that can enhance the longevity and resilience of coastal defence measures, while simultaneously decreasing the erosive forces.

Fig. 33. a) North Bevano (cell 71): Beach erosion (Feb. 5, 2014) (Aguzzi et al. 2020); b) Beach restoration following beach nourishment with offshore sand (Oct. 4, 2016) (Aguzzi et al. 2020).

⁴ <https://ambiente.regione.emilia-romagna.it/it/suolo-bacino/argomenti/difesa-della-costa>

From 1998 to 2012, several works were carried out, including longitudinal and transversal detached defence, modified in the following years and extended in 2020. These works were all carried out to the north of the NatuReef project area, using limestone rocks. In the area considered in the project only since 2014 there has been the installation of an internal embankment, repeated in 2020. Coastal defence works between the Fiumi Uniti and Bevano mouths in 2020 are shown in Fig. 34.

As reported in the publication “Stato del litorale emiliano-romagnolo al 2018” (Aguzzi et al. 2020), the area from the mouth of the Bevano River to the mouth of the Fiumi Uniti (cells 69–74) offers a difficult scenario. Sediment accumulation occurred in the south of the Fiumi Uniti mouth (cell 73), where the coastline advanced by 15–20 m over the period 2012-2018. During the same period, the beach at Lido di Dante (cell 72) also experienced an accretion, thanks to an integrated defence system made up of groynes and breakwaters, as well as the addition of 38,000 m³ of sand, 90% of which was deposited in 2016 as part of a regional beach nourishment project using offshore sand reservoir. As a result, the shoreline at Lido di Dante beach has advanced by 10-15 m. Furthermore, sand that is migrating to the parallel breakwater from the upper beach is occasionally transported back to the emergent beach by means of mechanical scrapers. An earth embankment at the higher portion of the emergent beach shields the nearby pine forest from flooding along the 2.3 km stretch between the Bevano mouth and the southern groyne of the Lido di Dante defensive system (cells 70 and 71), which is devoid of marine defence devices. The first 500 m to the north began to erode in 2006, and as this phenomenon grew worse over time, damaging the first km by 2012. As of 2018, the shoreline has receded by 10-20 m. The last 350-400 m, near the mouth of the Bevano, are being replenished and the shoreline is in equilibrium. The coastal defence works in this area in 2020 are shown in Fig. 34.

The subsidence rate in the area between the mouth of the Bevano and Lido Adriano exceeds 10 mm per year, with a maximum value of 17 mm per year in the Lido di Dante region, which represents the highest rate at the regional level.

Fig. 34. Coastal protection barriers in 2020.

5.2 New investigations

5.2.1 Digital Shoreline Analysis System DSAS

DSAS, initially developed by the United States Geological Survey (USGS) as an add-in for Environmental Systems Research Institute's (ESRI) ArcGIS, is a statistical tool instrumental in analysing both short-term and long-term coastal geomorphological changes. It calculates shoreline change rates using historical shoreline data, providing a statistical basis for analysing changes in shoreline position. DSAS computes various metrics such as the Net Shore Movement (NSM), End Point Rate (EPR) and Linear Regression Rate (LRR) to quantify shoreline movement (Himmelstoss et al. 2021). The software requires the user to specify the baselines for which statistics are to be calculated. The user must also enter the settings for the casting of transects (e.g. distance between transects) that intercept the available shorelines and along which these values are calculated.

5.2.1.1 Net Shore Movement NSM

The Net Shoreline Movement (NSM) is a measure used in coastal analysis to determine the total distance a shoreline has moved between two specific dates. It is defined as the distance (m) between the oldest and the youngest shorelines along each transect on which the DSAS analysis is performed. Unlike the End Point Rate (EPR), which normalizes this movement over time to provide a rate (m/year), the NSM simply indicates the absolute change in position without considering the time interval.

When the baseline is offshore, a positive value of NSM indicates that the shoreline has moved seaward over the investigated period and represents accretion or a gain in land area along the coast. A negative value indicates that the shoreline has moved landward over the investigated period and represents erosion or a loss of land area along the coast.

In coastal monitoring, the NSM provides a straightforward measure of shoreline change, helping coastal managers and researchers understand the magnitude of coastal processes over a specified period. It can be particularly useful in identifying areas of significant erosion or accretion, aiding in coastal zone management, hazard assessment, and planning efforts.

5.2.1.2 End Point Rate EPR

The End Point Rate (EPR) is a measure of the rate of change (m/year) of a shoreline between two specific dates. It is calculated as the distance between the position of the shoreline at two different points in time, divided by the time interval between these dates (Fig. 35).

Fig. 35. A shoreline dataset including baseline (black), transect (gray), and shoreline and intersect data (multicolour) to illustrate the relationship between shoreline change statistics: net shoreline movement (NSM), end point rate (EPR), and shoreline change envelope (SCE). NSM is the distance along the transect in meters (m) between the oldest shoreline (1936, red) and the most recent shoreline (2005, magenta). The EPR is the NSM distance divided by the time interval between the oldest (1936, red) and most recent (2005, magenta) shorelines (69 years in this example). The SCE (not used in the current analysis) is the greatest distance between all the shorelines regardless of date (Himmelstoss et al. 2021).

With an offshore baseline, a positive value indicates an advancement of the shoreline towards the sea, i.e., accretion or deposition. This means that the shoreline has moved seaward, typically due to sedimentation, while a negative value indicates a retreat of the shoreline towards the land, i.e., erosion. This means that the shoreline has moved landward due to erosion or loss of sediments.

In coastal monitoring, the EPR is a key indicator used to monitor coastal changes and can be integrated with other parameters and analyses to provide a comprehensive view of coastal processes and dynamics of the beach system.

5.2.1.3 Linear Regression Rate LRR

The Linear Regression Rate (LRR, m/year) is another metric used in shoreline analysis, particularly within the Digital Shoreline Analysis System (DSAS). It involves fitting a linear regression line to the positions of the shoreline over a series of time points. The slope of this line provides the rate of shoreline change over the analysed period.

Calculation of LRR (Fig. 36)

1. Data Collection:
 - o Collect shoreline positions at multiple time points.
2. Regression Analysis:
 - o Perform a linear regression analysis where the x-axis represents time (years) and the y-axis represents the shoreline position (distance from a baseline). Notice that, in case of an offshore baseline, the y-axis must contain negative values to show a positive slope corresponding to an accretion of the beach over time.
3. Slope of the Regression Line:
 - o The slope of the fitted linear regression line is the Linear Regression Rate (LRR).
 - o The LRR is usually expressed in meters per year (m/year).

Fig. 36. A shoreline dataset (baseline [black], transect [grey], and shorelines and intersects [multicolour]) presented on a map and as a graph of distance from the baseline versus the shoreline date in relation to the linear regression rate (LRR) regression line. The LRR was determined by plotting the shoreline intersect positions (distance from baseline) with respect to time (years) and calculating the linear regression equation of $y = 1.34x - 2587.4$. The slope of the equation describing the line is the rate (1.34 meters per year). LR2, R-squared of linear regression (Himmelstoss et al., 2021).

A positive LRR indicates that the shoreline is, on average, moving seaward over time. This suggests accretion or deposition processes are dominant. A negative LRR indicates that the shoreline is, on average, moving landward over time. This suggests erosion processes are dominant (for example, an LRR of -0.5 m/year means the shoreline is retreating landward by 0.5 m/year on average).

Advantages of Using LRR

- Trend Analysis:
 - Unlike NSM or EPR, which consider only two points in time, the LRR uses multiple shoreline positions to provide a more robust analysis of trends over time.
- Statistical Confidence:
 - The linear regression method provides statistical measures (e.g., R-squared values, confidence intervals) that indicate the reliability of the estimated rate.
- Temporal Patterns:
 - LRR can capture long-term trends and is less affected by short-term variability in shoreline positions, making it useful for understanding long-term coastal processes.

In the coastal monitoring, the LRR is widely used by coastal managers to:

- Identify long-term shoreline trends.
- Plan and implement coastal protection measures.
- Assess the impacts of natural processes and human activities on shoreline movement.

5.3 Coastline analysis of the Bevano river estuary, Ravenna

5.3.1 Materials and Methods

The coastline evolution and dynamics of the study area is assessed for the 1998-2019 and 2019-2023 time-intervals by using DSAS analysis as outlined by Himmelstoss et al. (2021) and described in paragraph 2. We divided the analysis into two distinct time periods, 1998-2019 and 2019-2023, due to the different spatial coverage and specific focus of each dataset.

For the 1998-2019 interval, shorelines were downloaded from the Regione Emilia-Romagna website. They were retrieved based on a mixed processing of orthophotos (using visual interpretation to delineate the coastline) and field DGPS surveys performed by ARPAE. Specifically, shorelines for years 1998, 2005, 2008, 2012, 2014, 2018 and 2019 were used. They have an accuracy of 5 m, a resolution of 1:5000 or 1:10000 and are all in the UTM32 coordinate system. More details on coastlines and download links are given in Table 7.

For the period 2019-2023, a detailed survey was conducted within the Life NatuReef framework along a limited coastal area located behind the forecasted reef location. The 2023 data are derived from a DTM obtained by two UAV flights performed over the beach with the DJI Matrice 300 RTK, 810×670×430 mm (without rotors), max. take-off weight 9 kg, with a max. payload of 2.7 kg, equipped with both payloads P1 (optical camera) and L1 (LiDAR sensor). The Digital Terrain Model (DTM) was generated with a resolution of 0.2 m by Proambiente (CNR) and the Geomatics research group of the Department of Civil, Chemical, Environmental and Materials Engineering (DICAM), University of Bologna. The zero value was used to extract the shoreline. The bathymetric baseline survey was performed on 2024-03-14 by Proambiente (CNR) and the Geomatics research group of the Department of Civil, Chemical, Environmental and Materials Engineering (DICAM), University of Bologna, with the use of a ASV (Autonomous Surface Vehicle) OpenSWAP (Stanghellini et al. 2020) equipped with a single beam echosounder. The topographic and bathymetric surveys were then merged to create one single digital surface model of the emerged-submerged beach.

As recommended in the DSAS Guideline (Himmelstoss et al. 2021) we created the baseline (Fig. 37) parallel to the coast and at a convenient distance so that it never met any fixed structures or the coast itself. We chose to create the baseline offshore (Fig. 37) and, based on the DSAS analysis, we used the LRR value to evaluate erosion and accretion in the 1998–2019-time interval, while for the 2019–2023-time interval we considered the EPR to estimate the rate of change between the two coastlines. As mentioned before, the EPR requires only two shoreline dates, and it is calculated by dividing the distance of shoreline movement by the time elapsed between the earliest and latest shoreline location. In the EPR analysis, a 90% confidence interval (CI) was defined. The CI represents the range within which the true shoreline change rate is likely to fall.

Topographic surveys of the dune-beach system were carried out at the site of interest within the NatuReef project since the project's beginning, one in November 2023 and the second in May 2024, across 11 transects perpendicular to the coastline (Fig. 38). In order to facilitate comparison between the state of the dune in the two different seasons and to monitor seasonal changes, GPS data were collected in both occasions along a second set of transects at the potential location of the reef (Fig. 38) using a Leica differential global positioning system (DGPS; Viva GNSS GS15 GPS) that worked with a real-time kinematic (RTK) system to ensure sub-metric accuracy. The GPS points were then compared with each other to check for any changes in the profile of the dunes that had taken place between the two seasons.

Table 7. Source and details of the shorelines used for the elaboration of the coastline evolution.

Year	Website	Source	Extension	Type of data	Download	Spatial resolution	Data source	Accuracy	Coordinate	EPSG
1998	website	Regione Emilia-Romagna	Regionale	OpenData - Vectorial & WMS	link	1:5000	Shoreline photointerpretation of the 1998 coastline flight.	5 m	RDN2008 / UTM 32N	7791
2005	website	Regione Emilia-Romagna	Regional	OpenData - Vectorial	link	1:5000	Shoreline photointerpretation of the 2005 coastline flight.	5 m	RDN2008 / UTM 32N	7791
2008	website	Geoportale Regionale	Regional	OpenData - Vectorial , WMS	link	1:5000	The 2008 version of the Land Use DB has the Agea 2008 and Agea 2011 orthoimages as its main source. The shoreline also contains coastal defence works or other artefacts	5 m	RDN2008 / UTM 32N	7791
2012	website	Arpae Emilia-Romagna - Servizio Sistemi Informativi	Regional	OpenData - Vectorial	link	1:10000	Mixed processing of AGEA 2011 orthophotos and Arpa 2012 survey	5 m	ETRS 1989 UTM Zone 32N	25832
2014	website	Geoportale Regionale	Regional	OpenData - Vectorial	link	N/A	N/D	N/A	RDN2008 / UTM 32N	7791
2018	website	Arpae Emilia-Romagna - Servizio Sistemi Informativi	Regional	OpenData - Vectorial	link	1:10000	Obtained by continuous survey c with dual-frequency GNSS satellite receivers, in RTK-OTF mode with base-rover positioning for differential correction.	5 m	ETRS 1989 UTM Zone 32N	25832
2019	website	Regione Emilia-Romagna	Regional	OpenData - Vectorial & WMS	link	1:5000	Mapping of the shoreline from photo-interpretation, according to RER methodology. The 2019 shoreline was drawn on the basis of the 2019 aerial images acquired by the Po River District Basin Authority, with the aid of the LIDAR DTM acquired at the same time as the aerial images.	5 m	RDN2008 / UTM 32N	7791

Fig. 37. Project baseline, used for erosion and accretion trend analysis with DSAS.

Fig. 38. GNSS topographic surveys of the dune-beach system carried out in November 2023 and May 2024 along the possible position of the reef

5.3.2 Vegetation assessment and identification

Vegetation plays a crucial role in the formation and stabilization of coastal dunes. Initially, it contributes to the formation of dunes by trapping wind-blown sand. Plants, particularly grasses and low shrubs, catch sand particles with their stems, leaves, and roots, leading to the gradual buildup of the dune structure. Pioneer species, such as beach grasses, are often the first to colonize bare sandy areas. Their adaptations to harsh coastal conditions allow them to stabilize loose sand and create a more hospitable environment for other plant species to establish. Once established, vegetation helps stabilize coastal dunes through its extensive root systems. These roots, which are often deep and fibrous, anchor the sand in place, forming a network that binds the sand and reduces erosion caused by wind and water. This stabilization is essential for maintaining the dune's structure over time. Moreover, vegetation reduces wind speed near the surface, which diminishes the potential for sand to be lifted and transported, thereby preventing further erosion. As vegetation grows, it also contributes organic matter to the sand, aiding in soil formation. Over time, the accumulation of plant material and decomposed organic matter enhances soil fertility and supports a diverse plant community, further stabilizing the dunes. In addition to these functions, healthy dune vegetation provides protection against storm surges and high waves. The physical presence of plant cover helps dissipate wave energy and reduces the impact of storm events on coastal areas (Merloni et al., 2015).

5.3.3 Leaf Area Index (LAI)

The Leaf Area Index (LAI) is a dimensionless quantity that characterizes the amount of leaf area in a given area. It is a critical parameter in understanding plant canopies and is widely used in fields such as ecology, agriculture, forestry, and remote sensing. LAI is defined as the one-sided green leaf area per unit ground surface area. For broadleaf plants, it includes both sides of the leaves, while for needleleaf plants, it includes only one side of the needles.

Mathematically, it can be expressed as:

$$LAI [-] = \frac{\text{Total leaf area [m}^2\text{]}}{\text{Ground area [m}^2\text{]}}$$

where the leaf area is the total surface area of leaves, and the ground area is the area of land over which the leaves are distributed.

LAI plays a crucial role in several ecological and agricultural processes. It is directly related to the photosynthetic capacity of plant canopies, which in turn influences the carbon cycle and plant growth. LAI affects water vapor exchange and energy balance between the canopy and the atmosphere, making it significant in the water cycle and climate regulation. It also serves as an indicator of habitat quality for wildlife, impacting factors such as food

availability and shelter. In agriculture, LAI is utilized to assess crop health and predict yields. Additionally, LAI is a key variable in satellite-based remote sensing, enabling the monitoring of vegetation dynamics on a global scale.

LAI can be measured via both direct and indirect methods. Direct methods involve physically removing and measuring leaves from a sample area. Indirect Methods include Optical Instruments, Allometric Relationships, and Remote Sensing: Satellites and aerial sensors capture images of vegetation, and LAI is estimated using spectral indices like the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) or other radiative transfer models. When using optical measurements, LAI can be estimated from the relationship between light intensity above the canopy (I_0) and below the canopy (I_1), typically using Beer-Lambert law:

$$LAI = \frac{\ln \frac{I_0}{I_1}}{k}$$

where k is a light extinction coefficient, which varies depending on the type of vegetation.

In remote sensing, LAI is often derived from satellite data through empirical models or radiative transfer models that relate observed reflectance or radiance to LAI.

Understanding LAI is crucial for studies related to plant physiology, ecology, and agricultural productivity, as it provides insights into the canopy structure and its interactions with the environment. LAI has various important applications across different fields. In forest management, monitoring LAI is essential for assessing forest health, planning harvests, and understanding forest dynamics. For climate studies, LAI data are crucial as they help model interactions between climate and vegetation, understand feedback mechanisms, and predict future climate scenarios. In agricultural practices, farmers use LAI to optimize irrigation schedules, fertilization, and pest control, with the ultimate goal of maximizing crop yields.

5.4 Results

5.4.1 Results of coastline change and evolution

The DSAS analysis shows different trends that define the coastal segment from the Fiumi Uniti to the Bevano estuary.

Fig. 39 illustrates the LRR values for the period 1998-2019 calculated with DSAS across the selected 175 transects. Two accretional areas were identified: one located in the northern sector and the other situated in the extreme

southern region near the Bevano River mouth. The northern accretional area is attributed to coastal breakwaters in front of the Lido di Dante beach that have effectively mitigated erosion and yielded a mean accretional rate of 0.74 ± 1.11 m per year (m/year). Erosional trends were observed in two distinct zones. The first encompasses a small area to the north, close to the Fiumi Uniti river mouth, while the second zone spans the central area, exhibiting a predominant erosion pattern across transect 98 and transect 175 (representing 56% of the total transects). Erosion is most pronounced in the central region, with a progressive decrease towards the southern extent. The mean erosional rate within the central area is -2.3 ± 0.99 m/year, transitioning towards negligible values in the southernmost segments.

The mean erosional rate is -1.49 ± 1.13 m/year in the project reef location from 1998 to 2019. Our update based on the 2023 surveys reveals that, between 2019 and 2023, a mixed pattern of both accretion and erosion occurred (Fig. 40). However, on average, there was a net accretion of 1.10 m/year.

Within the DSAS analysis we selected 6 transects (no. 62, 72, 82, 103, 113, 123) to provide an overview of the shoreline at the possible reef location and of the immediately northern area (Fig. 41). Fig. 42 a – f shows the EPR rate in the time interval 1998 - 2019 (to 2023 where available) for the selected transects, while Table 8 lists the NSM values for the same transects in the same period. Positive NSM and EPR values indicate an accretion, while negative values indicate erosion. It should be noted that in 2005 there was strong coastal erosion for all transects and that this trend is also present in more recent years (since 2019 or even earlier).

Fig. 39. Linear Regression Rate – LRR (m/year) for the period 1998-2019 (Map projection UTM33 WGS84).

Fig. 40. End Point Rate – EPR (m/year) for the period 2019-2023 (Map projection UTM33 WGS84).

Fig. 41. Selection of transects considered significant for assessing the state of the coastline in correspondence with and to the north of the possible reef location.

Fig. 42 a) – f) – EPR accretion and erosion rate [m/year] of a selected number of transects in correspondence with and to the north of the possible reef location. Note: graph f) shows the effects of coastal nourishment (vertical blue dashed lines) on the shoreline of transect n. 123, which is located at the possible reef location (increase in EPR value indicates an advancement of the shoreline).

Table 8. NSM (Net Shore Movement) values (m) of the selected transects

Transect	Year	NSM	Transect	Year	NSM
62	1998-2005	-35.5	103	1998-2005	-24.9
	2005-2008	19.6		2005-2008	7.5
	2008-2012	1.0		2008-2012	8.4
	2012-2014	-1.7		2012-2014	-25.1
	2014-2018	-8.6		2014-2018	5.2
	2018-2019	-16.6		2018-2019	-9.6
	2019-2023	N/A		2019-2023	N/A
72	1998-2005	-33.8	113	1998-2005	-11.0
	2005-2008	11.3		2005-2008	-0.8
	2008-2012	-17.9		2008-2012	5.3
	2012-2014	14.9		2012-2014	-13.3
	2014-2018	-18.0		2014-2018	1.9
	2018-2019	-10.3		2018-2019	-15.5
	2019-2023	N/A		2019-2023	N/A
82	1998-2005	-43.4	123	1998-2005	-17.2
	2005-2008	13.7		2005-2008	6.6
	2008-2012	-4.1		2008-2012	10.4
	2012-2014	-2.4		2012-2014	-16.9
	2014-2018	-14.5		2014-2018	-11.4
	2018-2019	-9.0		2018-2019	-14.9
	2019-2023	N/A		2019-2023	7.9

For transect 123, data were also available for 2023; Fig. 42f shows highly variable accretion and erosion rates (m/year) through the entire period as shoreline accretions occur following the beach nourishment projects carried out by the Region (blue dashed line in Fig. 42f).

Fig. 43 illustrates the LRR values calculated with DSAS. We found that the area of shoreline extending from the southern edge of the reef northwards for almost 2 km is in a state of severe erosion, while the areas outside this zone are stable or growing. As has been demonstrated in the northern sector of Lido di Dante, the installation of a barrier has the potential to disrupt the process of beach erosion, even though the observed accretion is largely attributed to the substantial beach nourishment initiative designated 'Progettone 4' (year 2022).

The LRR values of some example transects have been calculated individually and are shown in Fig. 43 a to d. The transects were selected in a manner that ensured representation of the area at the potential reef location, as well as the adjacent northern and southern region. Transects 42 and 162 were selected because they are outside the

erosion zone and are in fact characterized by positive LRR values (transect 42, growing zone) and close to 0 (transect 162, stable zone). In contrast, transects 82 and 123, already characterized previously and whose EPR and NSM are shown in Fig. 42 c and f, and Table 3 respectively, are located to the north and in correspondence of the possible reef location, respectively, in the erosion zone and therefore have negative LRRs.

Fig. 43. LRR values calculated for some representative transects, including: transect no. 42, situated immediately south of the Fiumi Uniti mouth at the outset of the study area, in an area characterized by accretion; transect no. 82, positioned just north of the potential reef location, in an area of erosion; transect no. 123, situated at the potential reef location, in an area of erosion; and transect no. 162, positioned to the south, in an area of stability. For transect 123, the information for the year 2023 is also available, in the graph shown in red.

5.4.2 GNSS topographic surveys and dune morphology

The comparison of dune profiles between winter and spring are shown in Fig. 44 a – k and indicates that, in most cases, there are no significant differences between the two seasons. Profiles 3, 4, 5, 6, 9 and 10 (Fig. 44 c, d, e, f, h, i) show no significant changes between the two surveys.

Profiles 1 (Fig. 44 a) and 8 (Fig. 44 g), however, show changes in the frontal dune slope, probably because they are the transects closest to the path, which could indicate anthropogenic disturbance, although access is limited here.

Profile 12 (Fig. 44 k) shows a change: in November it still has a low energy profile with a relatively wide beach in the backshore and a steep slope in the foreshore area. In March, after the whole winter season, there is a transition to a high energy profile with a reduction in volume from November to May. Profile 2 (Fig. 44 b) shows a similar behaviour in November 2023.

The presence of berm is noted in profiles 5, 6, 11, and 12 (Fig. 44 e, f, i, k). Berm is a flat or gently sloping area on a beach formed by wave action, typically between the active shoreline and the base of the dunes. It acts as a natural buffer, absorbing wave energy and protecting the dunes from erosion. In fact, the dune has vertical faces (almost vertical slopes), indicating that the coastal area is vulnerable to storm surges and coastal erosion. The dunes act as the first natural physical barrier against storm surges, wave energy, etc.

The greatest variations are observed in the northern transects (8-12). Since these areas are more exposed to the direct effects of NE wind (*bora* wind) and waves and there is less beach material to protect them, they are more variable.

Values for transect 7 are not available because the corresponding points were not sampled continuously across the different surveys.

Assessment in change of volume before and after the installation of the oyster reef will be evaluated by comparing the DTM carried out during the next project activities.

Figure 44. a) – k) – Dune profiles along 11 transects surveyed during two campaigns: November 2023 and May 2024.

5.4.3 Vegetation assessment and LAI measurements results

A field survey was conducted on 13th March 2024 to assess the presence and status of dune vegetation. The survey focused on the area of the dune situated in front of the potential reef site. Significant disturbance was evident, likely caused by repeated erosive events from waves, wind, and storm surges. This is also testified by the presence of several blowouts, erosional features caused by strong winds that remove sand from beneath and around vegetation, leaving behind sandy depressions without vegetation. These features can lead to increased dune erosion during storm events.

Starting from the shoreline, the beach appeared shallow, about 15 m at most, and without vegetation. Moving inland, woody debris deposited by storm surges (Fig. 45 a) accumulated near a vertical height difference of about 0.3 to 0.6 m, separating the beach from the top of the dune; the profile was steep and scarp-like (Fig. 45 b). At the top of the slope, the vegetation cover began but was sparse and poorly developed, characteristic of a disturbed environment. The Cakileto, typical avanduna vegetation, was absent, as was the embryo dune vegetation (*Agropyreth*). Scattered clumps of *Ammophila arenaria* were found at the top of the front dune, but they did not form a continuous belt; hence, while the species was present, the typical formation it created was absent. The 'Ammofileto was, in fact, disturbed, and much of the ridge was covered with *Cyperus capitatus*. This plant, typical of the Ammofileto, was favored over other species by the disturbance, particularly by the aeolian deposition of new sand, which was facilitated by the absence of a continuous *Ammophila* cordon. The *Cyperus capitatus* plants were still senescent, given the season.

Figure 45. a) & b) Woody material abutting the dune escarpment north of the central palisade of the study site.

Continuing beyond the dune crest, we encountered depressions typical of the backdune, where species from two distinct backdune habitats could be observed: the lowlands (habitat 6420) and the gray dunes (habitat 2130*). Although the micro-relief was modest, it likely promoted the presence of species from both habitats, which often appeared intermingled in mosaic patterns and rarely formed typical backdune biocoenosis. Species found in the relatively wetter lowlands included *Holoschoenus romanus*, *Erianthus ravennae*, and *Schoenus nigricans*. In contrast, species of the gray dunes, most abundant near the palisade along the cart road, included *Teucrium capitatum*, *Fumana procumbens*, and the mosses *Pleurochaete squarrosa* and *Tortula ruraliformis*.

The area south of the palisade divider, a protected zone, showed an even greater accumulation of woody material transported by storm surges (Fig. 46). The dune slope, if it existed, was completely buried by the deposited material and thus unrecognizable. The ridge featured the same vegetation distribution as the area north of the palisade, with scattered clumps of *Ammophila arenaria* and the dune predominantly covered with *Cyperus capitatus*. In the backdune, species typical of habitats 6420 (backdune lowlands) and 2130* (priority habitat gray dunes) were found, often combined in mosaic patterns. Species from the second habitat type were more abundant near the backdune. Notably, in each described situation, there was a conspicuous presence of non-native species such as *Oenothera stucchii*, *Ambrosia coronopifolia*, *Eleagnus angustifolia*, *Yucca gloriosa*, *Carpobrotus acinaciformis*, and *Cenchrus incertus*. These presences indicated the high degree of disturbance, both natural and anthropogenic, to which these areas were subjected.

Figure 46. a) & b) Woody material accumulated south of the central palisade of the study site. Note how the deposited material prevents the dune escarpment from being recognized.

The situation was like what was observed in November 2023. At that time, geomorphological surveys revealed a complete lack of embryo dune and pioneer vegetation, along with a scarp dune front throughout the entire study area (GNSS profiles in Fig. 44). Additionally, the southern zone contained a substantial amount of organic material, likely deposited after the May 2023 flood and never removed due to the absence of mechanical beach cleaning in this area.

The northern zone featured a narrower beach (approximately 10-15 m wide) compared to the southern zone (approximately 20-25 m wide), with the eroded dune displaying vertical slope (profiles 10 and 11 in Fig. 44). Coordinates for the plant species identified during the reconnaissance were also collected using DGPS and are listed in Table 4, while codes and descriptions of the identified habitats are reported in Table 9.

In general, the dune exhibited minimal vegetative cover, with sparse vegetation and expansive open spaces. The plant cover was limited or concentrated in a few areas. Many of the species present were underdeveloped and small in size.

Table 9. Identified plant species, place of identification and notes on habitat and its condition (survey conducted on 13/03/24). (Coordinate system: UTM Zone 33N)

X	Y	Elevation (m)	Plant species	Notes
286612.254	4916772.955	41.3	<i>Ammophila arenaria</i>	hab. 2120
286610.210	4916775.516	41.2	<i>Limbarda crithmoides</i>	
286605.092	4916774.968	41.0	<i>Elaeagnus angustifolia</i>	allochthonous
286615.871	4916785.396	41.8	<i>Ammophila arenaria</i>	hab. 2120
286607.968	4916805.568	41.4	<i>Cyperus capitatus</i>	hab. 2120
286607.173	4916836.617	41.7	<i>Ammophila arenaria</i>	hab. 2120
286607.007	4916840.953	41.8	<i>Euphorbia paralias</i>	hab. 2120
286591.938	4916835.927	41.1	<i>Teucrium capitatum</i> , muschi: <i>Pleurochaete squarrosa</i> , <i>Tortula ruraliformis</i>	hab. 2130*
286594.437	4916839.815	40.7	<i>Pinus pinaster</i>	hab. 2270
286593.070	4916840.890	40.6	<i>Oenothera stucchii</i>	allochthonous
286591.052	4916852.685	40.5	<i>Cistus</i> sp.	
286588.997	4916857.892	40.6	<i>Elaeagnus angustifolia</i>	allochthonous
286602.769	4916879.372	41.0	<i>Cakile maritima</i>	hab. 1210, disturbed
286601.989	4916880.204	41.2	<i>Salsola tragus</i>	hab. 1210
286594.455	4916889.639	41.1	<i>Xanthium italicum</i>	hab. 1210
286591.072	4916892.248	41.2	<i>Euphorbia paralias</i>	hab. 2120

X	Y	Elevation (m)	Plant species	Notes
286588.187	4916889.362	41.1	<i>Erianthus ravennae</i>	= <i>Tripidium ravennae</i> . (Canna di Ravenna) hab. 6420
286582.480	4916889.456	41.5	<i>Ammophila arenaria</i>	hab. 2120
286580.027	4916899.517	41.2	<i>Tamarix gallica</i> L.	South of the fence
286606.691	4916714.671	41.3	<i>Fumana procumbens</i>	hab. 2130*
286610.910	4916713.540	40.8	<i>Scirpoides holoschoenus</i>	hab. 6420
286626.839	4916682.548	41.6	<i>Euphorbia paralias</i>	hab. 2120
286624.955	4916668.715	41.6	<i>Ammophila arenaria</i> , <i>Cyperus capitatus</i>	hab. 2120
286628.295	4916663.325	41.4	<i>Medicago marina</i>	hab. 2110, 2120
286621.348	4916658.440	41.5	<i>Oenothera stucchii</i>	Dried + green plants
286609.280	4916661.299	41.2	muschi: <i>Pleurochaete squarrosa</i> , <i>Tortula ruraliformis</i> ; <i>Cyperus capitatus</i>	hab. 2130*
286612.194	4916640.675	41.1	<i>Phillyrea angustifolia</i>	hab. 2260
286629.030	4916631.231	41.3	<i>Yucca gloriosa</i>	allochthonous
286617.003	4916606.703	41.3	<i>Pinus pinaster</i>	hab. 2270
286618.220	4916579.154	41.1		hab. 2130* and hab. 2260
286633.234	4916597.326	40.9	<i>Carpobrotus acinaciformis</i>	allochthonous

Table 10. Habitat codes and their description.

2120	Shifting dunes along the shoreline with <i>Ammophila arenaria</i> (white dunes)
2130	Fixed coastal dunes with herbaceous vegetation (grey dunes)
2270	Wooded dunes with <i>Pinus pinea</i> and/or <i>Pinus pinaster</i>
1210	Annual vegetation of drift lines
6420	Mediterranean tall humid herb grasslands of the <i>Molinio-Holoschoenion</i>
2260	Cisto-Lavanduletalia dune sclerophyllous scrubs
2270	Wooded dunes with <i>Pinus pinea</i> and/or <i>Pinus pinaster</i>

LAI measurements were carried out with a Plant Canopy Analyzer (LI-COR LAI-2270C analyser, with GPS and a LAI2250 optical sensor) during November 2023 and May 2024 surveys. Table 6 summarizes the values recorded and their coordinates. The LAI was measured close to the vegetation, which, as mentioned in the previous chapter, is sparse and scattered along the dune. We measured LAI at different spots of the dune on different plant species,

which consequently have different leaf cover. There is indeed some variability in the results, although it should be noted that these values are generally very low. It should also be noted that the vegetation observed is quite short (only reaching a maximum of around 2 m in a few cases, mostly plant species were between 3 cm and 50 cm tall) and only partially covers the dune, which is completely uncovered in some areas.

Table 11. LAI measures. (Coordinate system: UTM Zone 33N)

Measure ID	Date	X	Y	LAI - Leaf Area Index	Notes
4	8/11/2023	286612	4916727	0.6	
5	8/11/2023	286610	4916721	2.5	
6	8/11/2023	286613	4916717	1	
7	8/11/2023	286612	4916713	2.7	
8	8/11/2023	286616	4916705	1.3	
9	8/11/2023	286614	4916695	6.2	
10	8/11/2023	286608	4916680	2.6	
11	8/11/2023	286616	4916652	5.5	
12	8/11/2023	286606	4916757	3.3	
13	8/11/2023	286613	4916762	1	
14	8/11/2023	286614	4916771	2.1	
15	8/11/2023	286610	4916775	3.1	
16	8/11/2023	286616	4916786	4.6	
17	8/11/2023	286602	4916794	1.9	
18	8/11/2023	286605	4916774	2.3	
21	9/5/2024	286607	4916730	3.1	
22	9/5/2024	286607	4916730	4.8	
23	9/5/2024	286611	4916714	3.6	
24	9/5/2024	286610	4916704	0.4	
25	9/5/2024	286612	4916693	1.9	
26	9/5/2024	286613	4916686	2	
27	9/5/2024	286613	4916676	2.5	
28	9/5/2024	286614	4916652	4.4	same point
29	9/5/2024	286613	4916651	4.1	
30	9/5/2024	286613	4916651	4.6	
31	9/5/2024	286616	4916627	3.6	
32	9/5/2024	286615	4916617	3.5	same point
33	9/5/2024	286615	4916616	5.3	
34	9/5/2024	286618	4916611	5.1	
35	9/5/2024	286627	4916593	3.9	
36	9/5/2024	286621	4916586	2.3	

Measure ID	Date	X	Y	LAI - Leaf Area Index	Notes
37	9/5/2024	286618	4916588	4.8	
38	9/5/2024	286617	4916588	6.2	
39	9/5/2024	286620	4916582	5.8	
40	9/5/2024	286618	4916576	4.5	
41	9/5/2024	286619	4916573	3.4	
42	9/5/2024	286623	4916572	2.1	
43	9/5/2024	286621	4916562	5.8	
44	9/5/2024	286629	4916556	2.8	
45	9/5/2024	286623	4916548	3.4	
46	9/5/2024	286645	4916539	5.4	
47	9/5/2024	286644	4916546	5.6	
48	9/5/2024	286640	4916555	8.1	
49	9/5/2024	286648	4916555	7.5	
50	9/5/2024	286636	4916560	5.7	
51	9/5/2024	286633	4916562	3	
52	9/5/2024	286627	4916566	3.8	
53	9/5/2024	286630	4916576	3.4	
54	9/5/2024	286626	4916597	2.9	
55	9/5/2024	286627	4916638	0	
56	9/5/2024	286616	4916701	4.8	
57	9/5/2024	286587	4916703	4.1	
58	9/5/2024	286572	4916700	4.4	
59	9/5/2024	286560	4916692	4.8	
60	9/5/2024	286606	4916757	3.9	
61	9/5/2024	286618	4916761	6.1	
62	9/5/2024	286613	4916768	1.5	
63	9/5/2024	286608	4916773	3.1	

6 Soft bottom habitats, communities, and biodiversity

6.1 Reference framework

The seabed of this area has been studied from an ecological point of view for the first time thanks to the FLAG project "Characterization of the mouth area of the Bevano stream and identification of conservation and enhancement strategies of nursery areas for protected species and species of commercial interest" financed by the Emilia-Romagna Region in implementation of the P.O. FEAMP 2014/2020 priority n.4 (OT.8), Action 2.A.a) "Marine and lagoon habitats - Studies and research" (Abbiati et al. 2019). Some subsequent surveys and samplings were carried out within the TAO project. Funded by the ROP-ERDF 2014-2020 of the Emilia Romagna Region, the TAO project aimed at developing innovative technologies to monitor the coastal belt in the «active» beach, in order to investigate the dynamic mechanisms causing the coastal erosion and to evaluate the effectiveness of the defence works (Stanghellini et al., 2022 Tagliabue et al., 2023).

6.2 New investigations

This report has benefited greatly from these previous investigations in terms of study methodologies and preliminary knowledge. However, this investigation specifically aims to provide the reference baseline to understand the effects of the introduction of the new habitat, oyster and sabellaria reefs, in the study area.

6.2.1 Macrobenthic assemblages

6.2.1.1 Sampling

To analyse the macrobenthic assemblages in the study area, defined considering the possible location of the designed reef, 40 sampling points were predefined, distributed in a semi-random way. Samplings were performed from 1 to 4 May 2024, and the actual sampling points were localised with a DGPS (precision 1 m, accuracy 2-3 m; Fig. 47; Table 12).

All samples were collected by scuba diving in a depth range between 0.5 and 5 m, during days with good weather conditions and calm to slightly rough seas. A plastic cylinder, with a diameter of 24 cm and an area of 452 cm², was used to circumscribe the portion of the seabed to be collected for each sample. The substrate sample was collected with the aid of a shovel, then placed in a bag and brought to the surface. Once on board the dinghy, an aliquot of approximately 50 ml was deducted from the sample thus collected, reserved for sediment analysis. The remaining part was sieved by rinsing in sea water using a net with calibrated holes of 500 µm. The fraction retained by sieving

was preserved in 95% denatured ethyl alcohol, intended for analysis of the macrobenthic component. The samples for sediment analysis were stored at -18 °C while those in alcohol were left at room temperature.

Fig. 47. Map of sampling points (Projection UTM33/WGS84).

Table 12. Sampling points (coordinates UTM33/WGS84).

Label	Sample	E	N
01-LIFENatuReefS2024	1	286832	4915905
02-LIFENatuReefS2024	2	286992	4915938
03-LIFENatuReefS2024	3	287051	4916036
04-LIFENatuReefS2024	4	287228	4915976
05-LIFENatuReefS2024	5	287170	4916117
06-LIFENatuReefS2024	6	287045	4916150
08-LIFENatuReefS2024	8	286878	4916102
10-LIFENatuReefS2024	10	286894	4916269
11-LIFENatuReefS2024	11	287057	4916270
13-LIFENatuReefS2024	13	287159	4916404
15-LIFENatuReefS2024	15	286816	4916386
16-LIFENatuReefS2024	16	286742	4916447
18-LIFENatuReefS2024	18	287056	4916512
19-LIFENatuReefS2024	19	287137	4916647
21-LIFENatuReefS2024	21	286833	4916536
22-LIFENatuReefS2024	22	286786	4916612
23-LIFENatuReefS2024	23	286908	4916678
24-LIFENatuReefS2024	24	286840	4916710
25-LIFENatuReefS2024	25	286829	4916789
27-LIFENatuReefS2024	27	287005	4916736

Label	Sample	E	N
28-LIFENatuReefS2024	28	287006	4916835
29-LIFENatuReefS2024	29	287105	4916935
31-LIFENatuReefS2024	31	286819	4916865
32-LIFENatuReefS2024	32	286835	4916960
33-LIFENatuReefS2024	33	286754	4916931
34-LIFENatuReefS2024	34	286696	4916875
35-LIFENatuReefS2024	35	286756	4916863
36-LIFENatuReefS2024	36	286735	4916806
37-LIFENatuReefS2024	37	286787	4916781
38-LIFENatuReefS2024	38	286735	4916729
39-LIFENatuReefS2024	39	286776	4916695
40-LIFENatuReefS2024	40	286717	4916659
41-LIFENatuReefS2024	41	286690	4916769
42-LIFENatuReefS2024	42	286671	4916961
43-LIFENatuReefS2024	43	286809	4917060
45-LIFENatuReefS2024	45	287000	4917144
47-LIFENatuReefS2024	47	286692	4917139
48-LIFENatuReefS2024	48	286668	4917279
49-LIFENatuReefS2024	49	286853	4917286
50-LIFENatuReefS2024	50	287057	4917321

6.2.1.2 Sediment analysis

Before proceeding with the organic substance analyses, the sediment samples were left at room temperature for the entire time necessary for their thawing. Once thawed, a portion of sediment was taken from each sample and placed in a crucible, previously weighed using an electronic analytical balance with a precision of 0.00001 g (Fig. 48). The crucibles, with the sediment inside, were weighed again and placed in an oven for 24 h at 80 °C. The samples, thus dried, were first left to cool in a dehumidification bell and then weighed to determine the loss of water content. Finally, they were incinerated in the muffle for 8 h of activity at 450 °C and then weighed to obtain the value of the loss of organic substance by difference in weight with the remaining ash (LOI, Loss on Ignition).

Fig. 48. Left: sediment samples during organic matter content analysis.

Macrobenthos samples were individually sorted under stereomicroscopes and each single specimen identified to the lowest possible taxonomic level based on morphological features at the optical microscope, ideally to species level, and counted (Fig. 49).

Fig. 49. Worktop with a) reflected light stereomicroscope, and b) high magnification transmitted light microscope.

6.2.1.3 Species diversity indices

Species diversity at each sampling point was calculated using 3 of the most common diversity indices (Magurran, 2004):

- Species richness (S);
- Species diversity (Hill's N1);
- Evenness (Hill's N10).

6.2.1.4 Spatial distribution

Species abundance was expressed as density (ind. m²), then abundances (and diversity indices) were interpolated in the study area. The interpolations were performed using the Ordinary Kriging (OK) interpolation algorithm because it can guarantee a good accuracy of the result when working with randomly distributed data and with moderately complex natural models (MacCormack et al., 2013). Furthermore, if compared with other algorithms commonly used in interpolations (e.g. Inverse Distance Weighted and Regular Spline), OK can provide a good prediction of intermediate values and with a minimum error (Zhang et al., 2015). Data were interpolated using the Surfer 11 software (Golden Software, 2012) using the default Kriging typology “Point Kriging” by setting the Grid Spacing value to 1 m and using the linear model, after checking the variogram. Finally, the representation of the spatial variability of the different parameters was carried out using the QGIS software ver. 3.34 (QGIS Development Team, 2024).

6.2.2 Phytoplankton and eDNA

To investigate phytoplankton and eDNA, both in the sediments and in the near bottom water, eight sampling sites were chosen to cover as much as possible the diversity of the coastal area involved. Points 5, 8, 15, 18, 28, 37, 45 and 47 were selected (Fig. 44, Table 12). Repeated, seasonal samplings have been planned to create a complete baseline of the area. A first sampling has been carried out in May 2024.

6.2.2.1 Sampling procedure and samples processing

At site n. 37, at the centre of the investigated area, environmental parameters (O₂ concentration, conductivity, pH and temperature) were measured with a multiparameter probe (HACH, USA).

At each sampling site, two types of matrices, water and sediment, were manually taken by scuba divers. Superficial water was collected in 2 Nalgene bottles of 1L. Bottom water samples were gathered using 1 L Nalgene bottles at the sediment-water interface through scuba diving. Sediment samples were collected immediately after water samples from the first centimetre of the sea bottom using 10 mL falcon tubes. To avoid contamination, bottles and tubes are previously sterilised with 70% ethanol alcohol (EtOH) and filled with deionised water. Both types of samples were maintained for no more than 6 h in a field mini fridge full of ice (dark and low-temperature conditions) to avoid eDNA denaturation and algae growth (Laramie et al., 2015). Both bottom and superficial water samples were held in a 4 °C dark room immediately after each sampling day, while sediment samples were stored at - 20 °C. Within less than 12 hours, two 500 mL aliquots of bottom and surface water samples were separately pre-filtered using sterile 3 µm cellulose filters (one filter for each 500 mL aliquot), followed by re-filtration through 0.22 µm sterile cellulose filters (one filter for each 500 mL aliquot). The filtered samples were then collected in sterile tubes and frozen at -20°C until eDNA extraction (Hinlo et al., 2017).

Furthermore, two aliquots of 400 mL of superficial water were filtered on GF/C nonsterile filters (one filter per each 400 mL aliquot) for chlorophyll content analysis. Filters are stored in 15 mL falcon tubes at -20 °C before analysis. Two aliquots of 250 mL from GF/C filtration flowthrough were kept for nutrients content analysis and stored at -20 °C until processing.

Aliquots of 200 mL superficial water were mixed with LUGOL solution and stored at room temperature in shaded glass bottles until qualitative-quantitative microscopy analysis of the phytoplankton community.

6.2.2.2 *Environmental DNA extraction*

The entire laboratory workflow was carried out under sterile conditions: use of self-protective instruments (lab coat, mask and gloves) and a sterilised working area (70% EtOH and 10% bleach). Bottom and surface water DNA extraction are performed using the DNeasy® Power Water Kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany) following the manufacturer's protocol. Sediment extraction was performed on 500 mg of each sediment sample using the NucleoSpin® Soil Kit (Macherey-Nagel, Germany) according to the manufacturer's protocol. DNA concentration was quantified using the dsDNA BR Assay Kit (ThermoFisher Scientific, Massachusetts, USA) and a Qubit 2.0 Fluorometer (Invitrogen, ThermoFisher Scientific Inc, USA). Samples with low DNA yield were concentrated using the NucleoSpin® Gel and PCR Clean-up kit (Macherey-Nagel, Germany) according to the manufacturer's protocol in a final elution volume of 30 µl. The following molecular markers were employed for the eukaryotic biological community screening: COI for most metazoans and 18S rDNA for non-metazoans.

6.2.2.3 *Chlorophyll-a content analysis*

Chlorophyll-a (Chl-a) was determined spectrophotometrically (UV/VIS, JASCO V-650, Tokyo, Japan), using 90% acetone as solvent for the extraction. A volume (10 mL) of acetone (90% v/v) is added to each tube containing the filter. Samples were vortexed until complete dissolution of the filter, then dark-incubated at 4 °C for 20-24 h. After incubation, 5 mL of solvent was added to the sample, then it was vortexed and centrifuged at 2550 × g for 10 min. The absorbance of the extract was measured at 750 and 665 nm and the concentration of Chl-a was calculated according to the equations proposed by Ritchie (2006).

6.2.2.4 *Nutrients concentration analysis*

Nitrate and phosphate analyses were performed on filtered water (Whatman GF/C filters, pore size 1.2 µm) and analysed spectrophotometrically (UV/VIS/NIR, JASCO V-650, Tokyo, Japan) according to Strickland and Parsons (1972).

6.3 Results

6.3.1 Marine sediments

In the area the sediments vary from sand, near the shore, to muddy sand, towards the open sea. The organic matter content in the sediments varies with the amount of mud and is influenced by the presence of the river mouth (Fig. 50).

Fig. 50. Organic matter in the sediments (Projection UTM33/WGS84).

6.3.2 Macroenthic assemblages

6.3.2.1 Macroenthic fauna

Overall, 85 taxa were found (Table 13). The most abundant taxonomic group in the area was polychetes, followed by bivalves.

Table. 13. Identified fauna.

Phylum	Class	Order	Family	Scientific Name	Authority
Annelida	Polychaeta	Spionida	Spionidae	<i>Prionospio cirrifer</i>	Wirén, 1883
Annelida	Polychaeta	Spionida	Spionidae	<i>Prionospio</i> cfr. <i>casperi</i>	Laubier, 1962
Annelida	Polychaeta	Spionida	Spionidae	<i>Microspio</i> sp.	Mesnil, 1896
Annelida	Polychaeta	Spionida	Spionidae	<i>Spio filicornis</i>	(Müller, 1776)
Annelida	Polychaeta	<i>incertae sedis</i>	Magelonidae	<i>Magelona papillicornis</i>	F. Müller, 1858
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Sigalionidae	<i>Sigalion mathildae</i>	Audouin & Milne Edwards, 1832
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Glyceridae	<i>Glycera alba</i>	(O.F. Müller, 1776)
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Glyceridae	<i>Glycera</i> sp.	Lamarck, 1818
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Nephtyidae	<i>Nephtys hombergii</i>	Savigny in Lamarck, 1818
Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Cirratulidae	<i>Chaetozone gibber</i>	Woodham & Chambers, 1994
Annelida	Polychaeta	<i>incertae sedis</i>	Maldanidae	<i>Euclymene</i> sp.	Verrill, 1900
Annelida	Polychaeta	<i>incertae sedis</i>	Maldanidae	<i>Euclymene oerstedii</i>	(Claparède, 1863)
Annelida	Polychaeta	<i>incertae sedis</i>	Capitellidae	<i>Notomastus</i> sp.	M. Sars, 1851
Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Onuphidae	<i>Onuphis eremita</i>	Audouin & Milne Edwards, 1833
Annelida	Polychaeta	<i>incertae sedis</i>	Oweniidae	<i>Owenia fusiformis</i>	Delle Chiaje, 1844
Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Serpulidae	Serpulidae n.i.	Rafinesque, 1815
Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Cirratulidae	Cirratulidae n.i.	Ryckholt, 1851
Annelida	Polychaeta	<i>incertae sedis</i>	Capitellidae	Capitellidae n.i.	Grube, 1862
Annelida	Polychaeta	<i>incertae sedis</i>	Maldanidae	Maldanidae n.i.	Malmgren, 1867
Annelida	Polychaeta	<i>incertae sedis</i>	<i>incertae sedis</i>	Polychaeta n.i. 1	Grube, 1850
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Hesionidae	<i>Oxydromus pallidus</i>	Claparède, 1864
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Nephtyidae	Nephtyidae n.i.	Grube, 1850
Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Nephtyidae	<i>Inermonephtys inermis</i>	(Ehlers, 1887)
Annelida	Polychaeta	Spionida	Spionidae	<i>Spiophanes bombyx</i>	(Claparède, 1870)
Annelida	Polychaeta	<i>incertae sedis</i>	<i>incertae sedis</i>	Polychaeta n.i.2	Grube, 1850
Annelida	Polychaeta	<i>incertae sedis</i>	<i>incertae sedis</i>	Polychaeta n.i.3	Grube, 1850
Annelida	<i>incertae sedis</i>	Sipuncula	Sipunculidae	Sipunculidae n.i.	Rafinesque, 1814
Phoronida	<i>incertae sedis</i>	<i>incertae sedis</i>	Phoronidae	<i>Phoronis muelleri</i>	Selys-Longchamps, 1903
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Cumacea	Bodotriidae	<i>Iphinoe trispinosa</i>	(Goodsir, 1843)
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Cumacea	Bodotriidae	<i>Iphinoe serrata</i>	Norman, 1867
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Cumacea	Bodotriidae	<i>Iphinoe armata</i>	Ledoyer, 1965
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Cumacea	Pseudocumatidae	<i>Pseudocuma (Pseudocuma) longicorne</i>	(Bate, 1858)
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Ampeliscidae	<i>Ampelisca brevicornis</i>	(A. Costa, 1853)

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Phylum	Class	Order	Family	Scientific Name	Authority
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Ampeliscidae	<i>Ampelisca</i> sp.	Krøyer, 1842
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Tryphosidae	<i>Tryphosa nana</i>	(Krøyer, 1846)
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Microprotopidae	<i>Microprotopus maculatus</i>	Norman, 1867
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Atylidae	<i>Nototropis swammerdamei</i>	(H. Milne Edwards, 1830)
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Atylidae	<i>Nototropis</i> sp.	A. Costa, 1853
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Bathyporeiidae	<i>Bathyporeia guilliamsoniana</i>	(Spence Bate, 1857)
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Corophiidae	Corophiidae n.i.	Leach, 1814
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Caprellidae	<i>Pariambus</i> sp.	Stebbing, 1888
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	<i>incertae sedis</i>	Amphipoda n.i.	Latreille, 1816
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Leucothoidae	<i>Leucothoe</i> sp.	Leach, 1814
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Oedicerotidae	<i>Pontocrates altamarinus</i>	(Spence Bate & Westwood, 1862)
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Cumacea	Nannastacidae	<i>Nannastacus</i> sp.	Bate, 1865
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Cirolanidae	<i>Eurydice pulchra</i>	Leach, 1816
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Urothoidae	<i>Urothoe pulchella</i>	(A. Costa, 1853)
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Corophiidae	<i>Monocorophium acherusicum</i>	(A. Costa, 1853)
Arthropoda	Ostracoda	<i>incertae sedis</i>	<i>incertae sedis</i>	Ostracoda n.i.	Latreille, 1802
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Diogenidae	<i>Diogenes pugilator</i>	(Roux, 1829)
Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Upogebiidae	<i>Upogebia stellata</i>	(Montagu, 1808)
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Myida	Corbulidae	<i>Lentidium mediterraneum</i>	(O. G. Costa, 1830)
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Venerida	Veneridae	<i>Chamelea gallina</i>	(Linnaeus, 1758)
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Lucinida	Lucinidae	<i>Lucinella divaricata</i>	(Linnaeus, 1758)
Mollusca	Bivalvia	<i>incertae sedis</i>	Thraciidae	<i>Thracia phaseolina</i>	(Lamarck, 1818)
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Cardiida	Tellinidae	<i>Peronidia albicans</i>	(Gmelin, 1791)
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Cardiida	Donacidae	<i>Donax semistriatus</i>	Poli, 1795
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Cardiida	Donacidae	<i>Donax venustus</i>	Poli, 1795
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Cardiida	Donacidae	<i>Donax trunculus</i>	Linnaeus, 1758
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Cardiida	Tellinidae	<i>Macomangulus tenuis</i>	(da Costa, 1778)
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Venerida	Mactridae	<i>Spisula subtruncata</i>	(da Costa, 1778)
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Venerida	Mactridae	<i>Mactra stultorum</i>	(Linnaeus, 1758)
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Adapedonta	Pharidae	<i>Pharus legumen</i>	(Linnaeus, 1758)
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Nuculida	Nuculidae	<i>Nucula nitidosa</i>	Winckworth, 1930
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Mytilida	Mytilidae	<i>Mytilus galloprovincialis</i>	Lamarck, 1819
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Galeommatida	Lasaeidae	<i>Hemilepton nitidum</i>	(W. Turton, 1822)
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Myida	Corbulidae	<i>Varicorbula gibba</i>	(Olivi, 1792)
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Arcida	Arcidae	<i>Bathyarca philippiana</i>	(Nyst, 1848)
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Nuculida	Nuculidae	<i>Ennuclia aegeensis</i>	(Forbes, 1844)
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Arcida	Glycymerididae	<i>Glycymeris</i> sp.	da Costa, 1778
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Venerida	Veneridae	<i>Ruditapes philippinarum</i>	(A. Adams & Reeve, 1850)
Mollusca	Bivalvia	Nuculanida	Yoldiidae	Yoldiidae n.i.	Dall, 1908
Mollusca	Gastropoda	Neogastropoda	Muricidae	<i>Hexaplex trunculus</i>	(Linnaeus, 1758)
Mollusca	Gastropoda	<i>incertae sedis</i>	Pyramidellidae	<i>Parthenina</i> sp.1	Bucquoy, Dautzenberg & Dollfus, 1883

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Phylum	Class	Order	Family	Scientific Name	Authority
Mollusca	Gastropoda	<i>incertae sedis</i>	Pyramidellidae	<i>Parthenina</i> sp.2	Bucquoy, Dautzenberg & Dollfus, 1883
Mollusca	Gastropoda	<i>incertae sedis</i>	Pyramidellidae	<i>Parthenina juliae</i>	(de Folin, 1872)
Mollusca	Gastropoda	Neogastropoda	Nassariidae	<i>Tritia neritea</i>	(Linnaeus, 1758)
Mollusca	Gastropoda	Littorinimorpha	Naticidae	Naticidae n.i.	Guilding, 1834
Mollusca	Gastropoda	<i>incertae sedis</i>	Pyramidellidae	<i>Auristomia erjaveciana</i>	(Brusina, 1869)
Mollusca	Gastropoda	<i>incertae sedis</i>	Pyramidellidae	Pyramidellidae n.i.	J. E. Gray, 1840
Mollusca	Gastropoda	<i>incertae sedis</i>	<i>incertae sedis</i>	Gastropoda n.i.	Cuvier, 1795
Mollusca	Scaphopoda	Dentaliida	Dentaliidae	<i>Antalis agilis</i>	(M. Sars, 1872)
Cnidaria	Hexacorallia	Actiniaria	Actiniidae	Anemonia n.i.	Risso, 1827
Chordata	Ascidiacea	Phlebobranchia	Ascidiidae	Ascidia n.i.	Linnaeus, 1767
Nemertea	<i>incertae sedis</i>	<i>incertae sedis</i>	<i>incertae sedis</i>	Nemertea n.i.	

On average, the most abundant taxa were the polychaete *Magelona papillicornis* (Table 14). It is an opportunistic polychaete, the distribution of which in the area seems to be strongly influenced by the presence of the river mouth, whose waters are diverted northwards by local currents (Fig. 51).

Table. 14. Most abundant taxa (mean, ind. m⁻²).

Taxon	Mean
<i>Magelona papillicornis</i>	2202
<i>Prionospio cirrifera</i>	1411
<i>Lentidium mediterraneum</i>	625
<i>Pseudocuma (Pseudocuma) longicorne</i>	408
<i>Prionospio</i> cfr. <i>caspersi</i>	156
<i>Chamelea gallina</i>	98
<i>Iphinoe trispinosa</i>	90
<i>Phoronis muelleri</i>	87
<i>Macomangulus tenuis</i>	54
<i>Owenia fusiformis</i>	45
<i>Thracia phaseolina</i>	34
Maldanidae	23
<i>Inermonephtys inermis</i>	23
<i>Donax venustus</i>	21
<i>Nephtys hombergii</i>	20

The second most abundant species was *Prionospio cirrifera*, a small opportunistic polychaete typical of these coastal areas (Fig. 51). Then we find the small bivalve *Lentidium mediterraneum*, typically associated with sand at 1-3 m depth (Fig. 52).

Fig. 51. Distribution of *Magelona papillicornis*, left, and *Prionospio cirrifera*, right (Projection UTM33/WGS84).

It is important to point out in the area a high abundance of small-sized clams, *Chamelea gallina*, a species of commercial interest that could find ideal conditions for reproduction here (Fig. 52).

Fig. 52. Distribution of *Lentidium mediterraneum*, left, and *Chamelea gallina*, right (Projection UTM33/WGS84).

6.3.2.2 Species diversity

In accordance with the availability of resources, the species richness tends to increase with the organic matter content in the sediments. The greatest overall diversity is found in the northernmost area. However, the less rich and structural assemblages have a greater evenness of individuals among the (few) species present (Fig. 53).

Fig. 53. Distribution species richness (S), diversity (N1), and evenness (N10) (Projection UTM33/WGS84).

6.3.3 Chlorophyll content

Chlorophyll-a content per each sampling point (noted as SP and sampling point number) was measured and reported in Fig. 54, highlighting low values ($4-7 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) of Chl-a.

Fig. 54. Chlorophyll-a content for each sampling point is reported as $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$.

6.3.4 Quali-quantitative analysis on phytoplankton

Microscopy analysis was performed on superficial water samples from each sampling point to identify the phytoplankton genera mainly present on the site. Data are noted in Fig. 55.

Fig. 55. Quali-quantitative analysis of the phytoplankton genera present in the superficial water samples collected at each sampling point. Percentage abundance (A) and abundance as cells mL⁻¹ (B) are reported.

The quali-quantitative analysis of the main phytoplankton genera at in all the sites highlighted a similar profile and the abundance of pennate and centric diatoms (i.e., *Nitschia/Pseudo-nitschia*, *Chaetoceros*, *Cylindrotheca*, *Navicula*, *Skeletonema*) which were present above 90%, while dinoflagellates (i.e., *Gyrodinium*, *Prorocentrum*, *Protoberidinium*) were present in low amounts (2 to 8 cells mL⁻¹).

7 Ornithofauna

7.1 Reference framework

Information on the current state of the ornithofauna present at the mouth of the Bevano river can be obtained from a broader picture, i.e. from the description of the fauna characterising the Natura 2000 Network site IT4070009 - SPA-SAC - Ortazzo, Ortazzino, Foce del Torrente Bevano. The Emilia-Romagna Region states that 44 species of birds protected by the Birds Directive 79/409/EEC are known to occur in the site, including the little egret (*Egretta garzetta*), the heron (*Egretta alba*), the flamingo (*Phoenicopterus ruber*), the Eurasian stone-curlew (*Burhinus oedipnemus*), the tawny pipit (*Anthus campestris*), the little tern (*Sterna albifrons*) and the kingfisher (*Alcedo atthis*). Of these 44 species, there are 20 breeding and 9 wintering species; all 44 species are also found to be resting during migration, 20 of which are exclusively passage birds. Most of these 44 species are linked to wetlands and are to be found in coastal ponds, in the overflowing meadows of river meanders, on beaches, and in open grassland environments; the nightjar and some passerines mainly frequent pine and shrub areas. Among the wetland-related species, many are dependent on lagoon and valley habitats, particularly about reproduction. Most of the bird species that frequent the portion of the site affected by the intervention do so for trophic reasons (related to nutrition) or for resting and shelter, in winter or during migration. There are few nesting species. The relationship of the various species with their breeding habitats is much closer than the relationship they have with the sites frequented for trophic or stopover reasons; the birds are much more adaptable in terms of trophic or stopover habitat than they are in terms of their choice of nesting sites. For two species in particular, the Eurasian stone-curlew and the Tawny pipit, the potential phenology is different from the observed phenology (phenology indicates how the various species are present in the area during the various periods of the year: nesting, wintering, sedentary, passage); in other words, these two species, although they have suitable habitats for reproduction at the site, do not nest there due to the presence of disturbing factors. In the case in point, the anthropic disturbance caused by the frequentation of the beach for bathing purposes affects the settlement of these species. The same factor also causes a presence far below potential for the little tern, which is an irregular and very localised nester (Bruschini et al. 2009).

7.2 New investigations

The census of the coastal and marine ornithofauna will include both protected and non-protected species, and their wintering and reproductive behaviours. Focus will be made to the Kentish plover, *Charadrius alexandrinus*^{*}, and the little tern, *Sternula albifrons*^{*} [* Priority species]. Surveys have been carried out by expert ornithologists with

repeated surveys in different seasons. The professional activity will be complemented by the collaboration with ornithological associations, as part of the public engagement and community-based monitoring foreseen in WP5. It is planned to carry out a monthly inspection during bird migration periods, in line with the census methods implemented by the park, in collaboration with ISPRA and AsOER, in the main wetlands of the Po Delta. The inspection is carried out along a selected transect within the study area (Fig 56).

Fig. 56. Study area (red line) and transect (yellow line).

In the most relevant periods for wintering and nesting, the detection intensity will be increased as follows:

- Wintering: two census visits, in the central part of the first and second half of the month (January); to these data will be added those collected by Parco, ISPRA and AsOER on the day of the International Waterbird Census.
- Nesting: two monthly survey visits, in the central part of the first and second half of each month, from April to July.

Total number of visits is 17. The determination and counting of wintering and migrating birds will be carried out by direct counting, with the use of 10x42 binoculars and 25-60x85 telescopes. The determination and counting of nesting birds will be carried out by detecting males singing for Passerines; direct counting, with the use of 10x42

binoculars, and analysis of behaviours proving nesting; nest counts for colonial species. Maximum attention will always be paid to not disturb nesting birds.

7.3 Results

The table below shows the data obtained during the inspections at the study area at the mouth of the Bevano river (Table 15 and 16). For each inspection, the date and time, the weather conditions, the species observed, the number of individuals observed for each species and any sources of disturbance have been recorded. On average, the ten most abundant bird species in the study period within the area includes *Sterna sandvicensis**, *Larus michahellis*, *Phalacrocorax carbo*, *Sterna Hirundo**, *Calonectris Diomedea**, *Larus ridibundus*, *Larus genei**, *Hirundo rustica*, *Anas platyrhynchos*, *Haematopus ostralegus* (Fig. 57).

Table. 15. Surveys at the study area.

N.	Date	Hour	Wind	Sky	Temp. °C	Rainfall	Sea	Tide	Disturbance
1	27/03/2024	7.00-10.00	Strong SE	Cloudy	6	Nothing	Moderate	High	Nothing
2	11/04/2024	7.00-10.00	Weak NO	Partially cloudy	12	Nothing	Smooth	Low	Nothing
3	26/04/2024	7.00-10.00	Weak SO	Partially cloudy	16	Nothing	Calm	Very low	Nothing
4	09/05/2024	7.00-10.00	Weak SO	Clear	18	Nothing	Calm	Very low	Nothing
5	28/05/2024	7.00-10.00	Weak S	Cloudy	18	Low	Calm	Very low	Nothing
6	06/06/2024	7.00-10.00	Weak O	Clear	24	Nothing	Calm	Very low	Nothing
7	26/06/2024	7.00-10.00	Weak O	Cloudy	26	Nothing	Calm	Low	Nothing
8	11/07/2024	7.00-10.00	Nothing	Clear	30	Nothing	Calm	Very low	Nothing
9	26/07/2024	7.00-10.00	Weak NO	Clear	30	Nothing	Smooth	Low	A person running in red zone
10	26/08/2024	7.00-10.00	Nothing	Clear	30	Nothing	Smooth	Low	Nothing
11	24/09/2024	7.00-10.00	Weak O	Clear	22	Nothing	Calm	Low	Nothing

Table. 16. Observed individuals during each survey (* priority species).

Species /Survey	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	Mean	SD
<i>Podiceps cristatus</i>	0	3	2	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0.5	1.0
<i>Podiceps nigricollis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0	0.0
<i>Phalacrocorax carbo</i>	3	29	27	7	29	15	25	25	12	7	54	21.2	14.6
<i>Microcarbo pygmaeus</i>	1	2	0	1	2	0	3	2	2	0	1	1.3	1.0
<i>Phoenicopterus roseus</i>	0	11	0	0	9	2	0	0	25	0	0	4.3	7.9
<i>Ardea cinerea</i>	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	2	0.4	0.7
<i>Ardea alba*</i>	0	4	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0.6	1.2
<i>Egretta garzetta*</i>	1	2	1	1	5	5	6	5	2	1	3	2.9	2.0
<i>Bubulcus ibis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0	0.0
<i>Phasianus colchicus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	1	0	0.3	0.6
<i>Tadorna tadorna</i>	0	5	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.6	1.6
<i>Anas platyrhynchos</i>	6	14	7	4	0	0	2	0	0	0	35	6.2	10.5
<i>Anas crecca</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	13	0	1.2	3.9
<i>Spatula querquedula</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0.4	1.2
<i>Pandion haliaetus*</i>	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.1	0.3
<i>Accipiter nisus*</i>	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.1	0.3
<i>Falco tinnunculus</i>	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.1	0.3
<i>Falco subbuteo</i>	0	0	1	0	2	0	1	0	0	1	0	0.5	0.7
<i>Calonectris diomedea*</i>	0	0	0	0	180	0	0	0	0	0	0	16.4	54.3
<i>Haematopus ostralegus</i>	15	4	10	7	5	7	2	3	1	0	1	5.0	4.5
<i>Himantopus himantopus*</i>	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.1	0.3
<i>Charadrius alexandrinus*</i>	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	2	0	0	0.4	0.8
<i>Charadrius hiaticula</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0	0.0
<i>Calidris alba</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.1	0.3
<i>Tringa totanus</i>	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.2	0.6
<i>Numenius arquata</i>	1	13	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1.5	3.8
<i>Numenius phaeopus</i>	0	0	4	2	0	0	1	3	0	0	0	0.9	1.4
<i>Stercorarius parasiticus</i>	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.3	0.9
<i>Larus michahellis</i>	36	47	44	45	42	91	29	37	39	23	11	40.4	19.9
<i>Larus ridibundus</i>	7	24	10	6	0	3	13	2	14	27	15	11.0	8.7
<i>Larus melanocephalus*</i>	0	16	0	6	1	0	0	13	0	0	0	3.3	5.9
<i>Larus genei*</i>	1	8	4	28	21	13	18	0	0	0	0	8.5	10.1
<i>Sterna hirundo*</i>	2	48	49	67	28	6	6	12	0	0	0	19.8	24.2
<i>Sterna sandvicensis*</i>	10	17	6	185	13	14	38	33	158	16	82	52.0	63.0
<i>Hydroprogne caspia</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.1	0.3
<i>Streptopelis turtur</i>	0	0	5	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0.6	1.5
<i>Columba palumbus*</i>	0	0	0	4	1	3	1	0	2	3	0	1.3	1.5
<i>Alcedo atthis*</i>	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0.2	0.4
<i>Upupa epops</i>	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.1	0.3
<i>Merops apiaster</i>	0	0	0	0	3	4	3	1	0	0	0	1.0	1.5
<i>Apus apus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0.4	1.2
<i>Oenanthe oenanthe</i>	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.2	0.6
<i>Hirundo rustica</i>	0	52	4	6	0	7	0	0	0	8	0	7.0	15.3
<i>Delichon urbica</i>	0	14	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	1.6	4.3
<i>Anthus spinoletta</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0	0.0
<i>Turdus merula</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0	0.0
<i>Phoenicurus phoenicurus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0	0.0
<i>Erithacus rubecula</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.1	0.3
<i>Sylvia melanocephala</i>	0	0	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	4	1	0.8	1.3
<i>Cettia cetti</i>	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0.1	0.3
<i>Pica pica</i>	2	1	0	0	0	1	3	1	0	0	2	0.9	1.0

The project LIFE NatuReef has been co-financed by the Programme LIFE 2021-2027

Species /Survey	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	Mean	SD
<i>Coracias garrulus*</i>	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0.4	0.5
<i>Corvus cornix</i>	0	3	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.4	0.9
<i>Sturnus vulgaris</i>	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.1	0.3
<i>Passer italiae</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0.2	0.6
<i>Fringilla coelebs*</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0	0.0
<i>Carduelis carduelis</i>	0	5	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0.6	1.6
Total	87	330	177	373	352	181	156	142	258	108	215	216.3	99.0

Fig. 57. Most abundant bird species in the area.

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